

State of knowledge regarding how we can improve adherence to the Mitigation Hierarchy, with a particular focus on the avoid stage

A report of the Eklipse Expert Working Group on the Mitigation hierarchy

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March 2023

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Sini Savilaakso¹, Joanna Storie², Beatriz Caitana³, C. Sylvie Campagne⁴, Daniel Depellegrin⁵, Davide Geneletti⁶, Ifigeneia Kagkalou⁷, Danica Lacarac⁸, Francesca Leucci⁹, Sandra Luque¹⁰

- 1 Department of Forest Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry, Helsinki, Finland
- 2 Department of Landscape Architecture, Estonian University of Life Sciences, Estonia
- 3 Centre for Social Studies at the University of Coimbra - CES/UC, Portugal
- 4 Station Biologique de Roscoff, CNRS and the Sorbonne University, Paris, France
- 5 Department of Geography, University of Girona, Spain
- 6 Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, Italy
- 7 Protection of the Aquatic Environment- Ecology
Department of Civil Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece
- 8 The National Green Roof Association, Serbia
- 9 University of Bologna, Department of Economic Sciences, Italy, University of Rotterdam,
Institute of Law and Economics, Netherlands, University of Hamburg, Institute of Law and Economics,
Germany
- 10 National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food & the Environment (INRAE), Unit Land, environment,
remote sensing and spatial information, France

Authors contribution statement:

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Reviewers of the methods protocol:

Fabien Quétier – Biotope, France
 Wolfgang Schuster – MaRenate, Germany
 Sanne Vammen Larsen – Aalborg University, Denmark
 Karl Schlagbauer – Brunel University, UK
 Anonymous reviewer 1
 Anonymous reviewer 2

Reviewers of the synthesis report:

Joseph Bull – University of Oxford, UK
 Madli Linder – Estonian Environment Agency, Estonia
 Sanne Vammen Larsen – Aalborg University, Denmark
 Nicolas Hette-Tronquart – French Agency for Biodiversity, France
 Lawrence Jones-Walters – Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands
 Anonymous reviewer 1
 Anonymous reviewer 2

Series editors: Karla E. Locher-Krause, Onno Knol, Agnes Zolyomi, and Marie Vandewalle

Editorial Design: Mira Antonijevic, www.jutro-design.de

EKLIPSE TEAM

Members of Knowledge Coordination Body:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Onno Knol – Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL), The Netherlands. ■ Agnes Zolyomi - Ecosystem Evaluation
Members of the Methods Expert Group:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Alister Scott – University of Northumbria, UK ■ Lyudmyla Zahvoyska – Ukrainian National Forestry University, Ukraine; University of Valladolid, Spain
Member of the Eclipse Management Body:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Karla E. Locher-Krause – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Germany

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Glossary

Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION	KEY REFERENCES
Avoidance	The first step of the mitigation hierarchy comprises measures taken to avoid creating impacts from the outset, such as careful spatial or temporal placement of infrastructure or disturbance. For example, the placement of roads outside of rare habitats or key species' breeding grounds, or by timing of seismic operations when aggregations of whales are not present.	The Biodiversity Consultancy, 2021, Ekstrom et al., 2015
Avoidance measure (French legislation)	<i>Les articles 2 et 69 codifient des éléments de la doctrine nationale ERC dans le code de l'environnement et enrichissent les principes de la séquence ERC avec une définition de la séquence ERC qui hiérarchise les trois phases (L. 110-1); Les lignes directrices sur la séquence ERC définissent la mesure d'évitement comme étant une « mesure qui modifie un projet ou une action d'un document de planification afin de supprimer un impact négatif identifié que ce projet ou cette action engendrerait ».</i> Articles 2 and 69 codify elements of the national mitigation hierarchy (ERC in French for Eviter Réduire Compenser) doctrine in the French Environmental Code and augment the principles of the mitigation hierarchy with a definition of the mitigation hierarchy that prioritises the three phases (L. 110-1); The guidelines on the mitigation hierarchy define an avoidance measure as "a measure that modifies a project or action in a planning document in order to eliminate an identified negative impact that this project or action would cause".	French law on the reconquest of biodiversity (n° 2016-1087 of 8 August 2016)
Applied Policy Delphi	This method is a subset of expert consultation, representing the most rigorous approach to eliciting expert knowledge. It combines the knowledge of multiple, carefully selected experts into either quantitative or qualitative assessments, using formal consensus methods such as the Delphi process (described and reviewed by Mukherjee et al. 2016) or other elicitation techniques, including Cooke's method for weighting experts for their accuracy, described in Martin et al. (2012).	Eclipse, 2021
Ecosystem Services (ES)	Contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being, such as flood protection and harvestable products. Ecosystem services can be categorised into provisioning, cultural, regulation and maintenance services.	Haines-Young, R. and M.B. Potschin, 2018
Exposure	A proposed management regime, policy, action or environmental variable to which the subject populations are exposed.	Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2018
Impact avoidance	The first part of the mitigation hierarchy, avoidance or prevention, refers to the consideration of options in project location, siting, scale, layout, technology and phasing to avoid impacts on biodiversity, associated ecosystem services, and people. This is referred to as 'the best option', but it is acknowledged that avoidance or prevention is not always possible. Impact avoidance requires developers to 'anticipate and prevent adverse impacts on biodiversity before actions or decisions are taken that could lead to such impacts' (Ekstrom et al., 2015). Impact avoidance is typically identified as the most important stage of the mitigation hierarchy (McKenney & Kiesecker, 2010; Clare et al., 2011; Ekstrom et al., 2015).	Lukey and Paras, 2017, Phalan et al., 2018
Impact assessment	Impact assessment (IA) is a structured process for considering the implications, for people and their environment, of proposed actions while there is still an opportunity to modify (or even, if appropriate, abandon) the proposals. It is applied at all levels of decision-making, from policies to specific projects.	International Association for Impact Assessment https://www.iaia.org/wiki-details.php?ID=4
Impact evaluation	An impact evaluation provides information about the observed changes or 'impacts' produced by an intervention. These observed changes can be positive and negative, intended and unintended, direct and indirect. An impact evaluation must establish the cause of the observed changes. Identifying the cause is known as 'causal attribution' or 'causal inference'.	Better Evaluation https://www.betterevaluation.org/methods-approaches/themes/impact-evaluation

TERM	DEFINITION	KEY REFERENCES
Mitigation hierarchy	The sequence of actions to anticipate and avoid impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Where avoidance is not possible, the aim is to minimise the impacts. When impacts occur, the preferred options are to rehabilitate or restore. In a case where significant residual impacts remain, off-setting is recommended.	Ekstrom et al., 2015
Multiple stakeholder engagement	The participation of multiple stakeholders implies the active involvement of stakeholders at different stages of the decision-making process, in the strategies for capacity building, and in the sharing knowledge environment. It is expected that the engagement is undertaken in a transparent way. This approach provides opportunities for co-production and co-governance to emerge and ensures stakeholder contributions for a just and inclusive transition.	EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 European Green Deal
Natural capital	Natural capital can be defined as the world's stocks of natural assets, which include geology, soil, air, water and all living things. These assets are considered essential to the long-term sustainability of development for their provision of "functions" to the economy, as well as to mankind outside the economy and other living beings.	World Forum on Natural Capital (https://naturalcapitalforum.com/about/) and Glossary of Environment Statistics, Studies in Methods, Series F, No. 67, United Nations, New York, 1997.
Nature's contributions to people	Nature's contributions to people (NCP) are all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (i.e. diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to the quality of life for people.	IPBES Glossary https://ipbes.net/glossary
Systematic mapping approach	Structured, stepwise methodology following an <i>a priori</i> protocol to comprehensively collate and describe existing research evidence (traditional academic and grey literature).	Eclipse, 2021
Vulnerable areas	Vulnerable areas in this report are those areas that are not part of a protected area but are still considered at risk of losing valuable biodiversity, habitat or ecosystem services.	Toivonen et al. (2021)

Summary

1. Summary and recommendations

1.1 Summary

The Mitigation Hierarchy is the sequence of actions (avoid-minimise-restore-compensate) to anticipate and avoid adverse impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. The avoid or prevent stage is the first and most important stage of the mitigation hierarchy in which developers anticipate adverse impacts on biodiversity before actions or decisions are taken. Action is then taken to prevent adverse impacts by considering different options in the project location, scale, layout, technology and phasing. Avoidance is often the easier, cheaper and more effective way than trying to restore a damaged habitat or offset elsewhere. The Mitigation Hierarchy application is mandatory in France, however, the French Biodiversity Agency put a request to Eklipse to find out to what extent the adherence to and implementation of the hierarchy is correctly applied and ecosystem services are considered and well documented.

To answer this request, an Expert Working Group on Mitigation hierarchy was established to answer three main questions:

1. To gather knowledge on how ecosystem services/natural capital as concepts foster the conservation and enhancement of biodiversity within planning processes in sectors that are likely to have a direct impact on biodiversity, e.g., infrastructure development, resource use and land use change.
2. To identify EU-wide cases and practices that actively consider and address the aspect of ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy, for example, in natural capital assessments, impact assessments of projects, plans, programmes, policies or similar processes.
3. To develop guidance on best practices and information on:
 - a. If and how the consideration and operationalisation of ecosystem services can be integrated into natural capital assessments, impact assessments, and policymaking processes to enhance biodiversity conservation as well as to understand the risks and potential ecosystem service trade-offs involved.
 - b. What kind of outcomes, impacts, challenges, solutions, etc., may occur when the ecosystem services concept is used in the natural capital assessments, impact assessments, mitigation hierarchy and similar processes?
 - c. The level of replicability/transferability of suggested/known tools/guidance/processes in other countries or regions that have been used successfully in the avoid stage.

Three steps were implemented to answer the questions:

- i) A systematic mapping approach was used to provide an overview of the available evidence and knowledge gaps.
- ii) An Applied Policy Delphi process for deliberative consultation, discussion, and feedback.
- iii) An analysis of results and conclusions based on the findings from the systematic mapping and the Applied Policy Delphi.

Below, a summary of the research findings is presented and discussed. We then provide recommendations based on the outcomes of this investigation.

Quality of evidence and knowledge gaps

From the systematic mapping, there were 45 papers that explicitly mentioned the mitigation hierarchy. Our research found that most mitigation hierarchy studies covered terrestrial environments, with a lack of studies on marine and freshwater environments. Geographically, studies from Eastern Europe are lacking. Although the concept of the mitigation hierarchy is relatively well known, the number of studies of mitigation hierarchy in practice was small, especially those applying the ecosystem services approach. There was also a lack of studies on risks, trade-offs and impacts, as well as educational and capacity-limiting factors. Overall, ecological aspects of avoid and mitigation stages have been studied more than social or governance aspects. However, to succeed in using mitigation hierarchy to its full potential, a more holistic understanding of all these aspects is needed. An Applied Policy Delphi process supplemented the literature to address knowledge gaps and produce a report based on the best available evidence that also acknowledges where differing views occur to give an unbiased perspective.

Enhancing landscapes through the use of mitigation hierarchy

Understanding and implementing the concept of mitigation hierarchy in practice needs strengthening, especially at the avoid stage, to protect the remaining natural ecosystems, as they are irreplaceable habitats. Managed landscapes also need to be enhanced to achieve overall net biodiversity gains. We, therefore, suggest embracing the positive concept of landscape-level enhancement (i.e., improving landscapes for biodiversity and ecosystem services) as an umbrella term to frame a biodiverse future that brings multiple benefits to society. We need to assess and act proactively to avoid, minimise or restore our landscapes to ensure nature-positive developments with net gains for biodiversity and human wellbeing.

Addressing drivers to avoid impacts

Regulations and policies

Regulations and policies are key to strengthening enforcement of the mitigation hierarchy and ensuring effective avoidance of impacts. Our results support a stronger, more consistent regulatory approach to the mitigation hierarchy from the EU to national levels as an overarching principle in land-use planning as well as in conservation. The evidence suggests that voluntary standards can support and provide guidance on impact avoidance but cannot be relied upon alone. In addition, there was consensus that a stronger focus should be put on avoidance and minimisation rather than offsetting. Based on the results and feedback, our recommendation is that the mitigation hierarchy should be firmly established in law in all EU countries following the example of France, and the precautionary principle should be better implemented where scientific data on biodiversity are missing.

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Protecting biodiversity requires an understanding of the ecology of ecosystems.

Social drivers of avoidance

Conflicts often arise from the different values and perspectives that people have for nature and their local environment, yet in nearly all case studies, community-based stakeholders were not included. Including these varying perspectives requires active and institutionalised involvement of different stakeholders. Improving the appreciation of the ecosystem services concept by citizens and decision-makers requires the identification of clear strategies and consensus building, with the possibility to influence, negotiate and deliberate on decisions by all stakeholders. Stakeholder mapping and analysis can support the identification of the stakeholder groups, their level of influence, the activities that already exist and, more importantly, how to engage them. Attention to inclusiveness helps bring priority groups currently under-represented into the dialogue, building trust if done well.

Mainstreaming ecosystem services as part of the mitigation hierarchy

Panel debates and results from literature largely agree that ecosystem services should be mainstreamed in the mitigation hierarchy processes to address biodiversity values from a broader perspective, raise awareness of the societal benefits of nature conservation, and highlight the livelihood dependency on nature. The integration provides an opportunity to connect biodiversity issues with social challenges better. Integrating ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation underlines that biodiversity is essential to support all ecosystem services and that conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of ecosystems and their services are part of the same issue. However, concerns were raised that the inclusion of ecosystem services risked being disadvantageous to biodiversity, particularly in cases where provisioning services, for example, can be easily measured and quantified versus those services with non-monetary benefits.

Effective avoidance: what to avoid and how to do it

It is clear from the results that a proactive approach to ensure effective avoidance is needed. One approach is landscape-scale mapping of biodiversity and sensitive ecosystems along with their relevant ecosystem services. This brings scientists and stakeholders together in a mutually inclusive learning process, linking expert and local knowledge(s) with the aim to implement meaningful territorial strategies and build local capacity to understand and implement the strategies.

A multi-species approach is also needed to consider the mobility of species through the landscape and their varying sensitivity to habitat fragmentation using a habitat connectivity framework. Trade-offs are inevitable and need to be identified and

managed in a transparent manner. However, it is easier to minimise these trade-offs at the landscape scale to ensure the maximum ecological benefit for a greater number of species. Landscape mapping of the functional ecological units can highlight where further fragmentation of the landscape can be avoided and draw attention to the potential threats from multiple sources as well as their cumulative impacts. The development of blue and green infrastructure as buffer zones also has the potential to support biodiversity and a range of ecosystem services.

An Applied Delphi panellist stated that in practice, the alternatives to avoidance are never costly enough and therefore, offsets are regularly used to compensate for biodiversity loss. A landscape-scale analysis, therefore, should identify these irreplaceable areas and the necessary green infrastructure to support their integrity and the species that depend on them before any offsets should be considered.

Effective avoidance from infrastructure projects

Effective avoidance of impacts from infrastructure projects must take into account pressures on both biodiversity and societal dimensions. A pressure framework is useful here, as in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, to formalise avoidance measures into spatio-temporal terms (pressure and intensity-based avoidance buffers, wildlife-specific avoidance buffers, and seasonal avoidance buffers); define the pressure propagation patterns (e.g., buffers of influence) and highlight the sensitivity of biodiversity components to the pressures addressed. Technological innovations and design can, in some cases, alleviate infrastructure project impacts on biodiversity; however, they may bring with them uncertainty with new and diversified pressures and pressure mechanisms. The cancellation of infrastructure projects should be considered if the process generates high uncertainty of impacts on biodiversity and society.

Improving implementation through stakeholder engagement and capacity building

The complexity inherent within ecosystems also presents a significant barrier to the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy in land-use planning, where assessments tend to focus on the flow of benefits to people and so fail to recognise the current and future role of biodiversity. This complexity and the dynamic nature of the systems, therefore, need clear definitions and terminology to ensure common understanding, paying particular attention to translating technical language. However, it is also important to construct narrative accounts that are specific to a place, as each landscape unit presents unique challenges to biodiversity and the people who live

and work in that landscape. Building the capacity to understand this natural capital across sectors and stakeholder groups is critical, but there are several challenges, including, for example, the limited knowledge of the participants, the loss of motivation of the public authorities and organisations, and insufficient funding for implementation, requiring significant investments of time and funding to address. It was also underlined that transparency and equity are crucial for validation, enforcement and monitoring. It is recommended from the results that active participation should be encouraged by raising awareness through better background information about the ecological status of the ecosystems and by appropriate communication channels to engage the different stakeholder groups.

Conclusion

Finally, we conclude that putting biodiversity first and avoiding further loss is both possible and needed for the benefit of society, the economy and the planet we live on. Moving towards sustainability requires fundamental transformations, including changes in how biodiversity is perceived and valued. Newly established relations between societal actors are also required. The recommendations in this report provide a roadmap on how to do this. However, they are only effective if decision-makers, land use planners and practitioners commit to improving legislation and practices. Hence, we urge all those involved in land-use planning, development and natural resource use: it is time to act to get effective mitigation practices into place before tipping points are reached.

Drone overview of hydrological catchment and agricultural intensification on the limitation of the surface water pollution by phytosanitary products Ru des Effervettes, Department of Seine et Marne (France).

photo © Samuel Alleaume

1.2 Recommendations

It is clear from the evidence presented in this report that there is room for improvement in understanding and implementing the concept of mitigation hierarchy in practice. There is a need to ensure the strengthening of the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy, especially the avoid stage, to protect remaining natural ecosystems as they are irreplaceable habitats. To achieve effective avoidance at the country level, we recommend a holistic approach that targets the underlying drivers of avoidance (e.g., policies and regulations) alongside improving practices to use the mitigation hierarchy. The recommendations below are derived from the evidence we found both in the literature and through expert

engagement. Our first recommendation on legal requirements is a medium to long-term ambition. However, others are actions that land use planners, local authorities, and those working on implementing the mitigation hierarchy can take on a board immediately. In addition, we make recommendations for researchers and educational institutes that target knowledge gaps found in the evidence and support strengthening the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy. For ease of reference, we have added the section numbers in parentheses after each recommendation.

Recommendations

-
01 Create overarching **minimum legal requirements** (i.e. Biodiversity Law) and **guiding principles** for systematic application of mitigation hierarchy in all sectors.
-
02 Decide **where to avoid or minimise** in land-use planning processes.
-
03 **Include stakeholders** at the beginning of the planning, design and implementation phases.
-
04 Address **different impacts** on biodiversity and ecosystem services during planning processes.
-
05 Address **connectivity and cumulative** impacts during planning processes.
-
06 Champion **capacity building** to ensure effective implementation and monitoring of the results.

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Strengthening regulations and their implementation would ensure vulnerable species and habitats are protected.

1.2.1. Create overarching minimum legal requirements (i.e., Biodiversity Law) and guiding principles for the systematic application of mitigation hierarchy in all land and resource use sectors (4.1.5, 4.2.4, 4.3.6, 5.3).¹

- This should happen at all levels starting from the EU level.
- Policymakers at the EU level should:
 - Improve existing guidelines to strengthen the application of the avoid stage of the mitigation hierarchy in areas protected under EU law.
 - Strengthen the application of the Precautionary Principle where a threat to biodiversity is foreseeable but scientific information is unavailable.
 - Ensure that the principles of EU environmental law (i.e., EU law primacy, effectiveness, integration, precautionary, polluter pays) are fully utilised in key regulatory and voluntary tools aimed at implementing the mitigation hierarchy in a harmonised way throughout the EU.
 - Ensure that national restoration plans developed to implement the recent proposal for a Nature Restoration Law at the EU level take into account the recommendations listed below, especially when designing renewable energy go-to areas.²
- Legislation at national level in each country should include, at a minimum:
 - A clear and harmonised definition of the scope and the goal of the mitigation hierarchy.
 - A definition of relevant avoidance and minimisation measures.
 - Mandatory registers for monitoring and disclosure of the wider mitigation hierarchy processes (not just offsetting) to ensure implementation happens in practice.
 - Technical guidance for land use planners, project developers, etc., to help operationalise the legislation.
 - Regulatory commitment to finance sufficient resources for effective implementation and monitoring of the results.
- Support the uptake and effective implementation of the mitigation hierarchy by creating national supporting bodies and/or a Europe-wide community of practice to share experiences and best practices and help knowledge transfer.

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Planning decisions should capture and integrate the priorities and needs of different stakeholders.

¹ Numbers in parentheses refers to the sections in the report relevant to the recommendations

² The recent Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration of 22 June 2022 provides at p. 30, par. 61: In the designation of renewables go-to areas, Member States should avoid protected areas and consider their national nature restoration plans.

1.2.2. Decide where to avoid or minimise in land-use planning processes (4.1.4, 4.1.6, 4.2.2, 4.2.5, 4.3.2, 4.3.3, 5.4).

■ Land-use planners:

- Ensure mapping of biodiversity and ecosystem services at the local and regional level, paying particular attention to irreplaceable areas of high biodiversity and vulnerable areas in terms of both biodiversity and ecosystem services where impact avoidance needs to be enforced.
- Provide measures and scenarios based on multiple habitats and multiple species to integrate spatial and temporal dynamics into a connectivity approach. This approach should aim to improve the overall ecological network and provide a set of ecosystem services.
- Ensure mapping of ecosystem services takes into account the conditions of ecosystems, for example, through the methodologies and indicators proposed by the European Commission in the 2022 report “EU-wide methodology to map and assess ecosystem condition”.³
- Manage surrounding blue and green infrastructure networks more effectively and ensure multi-functionality. Aim to support and connect protected and vulnerable areas by using restorative processes, support traditional semi-natural management techniques and introduce high-quality green areas using indigenous and sensitive planting, i.e. planting in-keeping with the ecology of the area and avoiding expansive species.

■ National, sub-national and local authorities:

- Invest in mapping ecosystem services, especially in the marine space where data on biodiversity is missing. This will improve the data available on the benefits to society, leading to better evidence-based policymaking.
- Employ a mix of mandatory and voluntary tools, e.g. taxation, in order to strengthen avoidance, thus protecting valuable habitats.

1.2.3. Include stakeholders at the beginning of the planning, design and implementation phases (4.1.2, 4.2.6, 4.3.4, 5.3.2, 5.5).

■ Engage and include stakeholders at the beginning of the planning and design phase by recognising the plurality of forms of knowledge and establishing dialogue, especially in areas where there are potentially conflicting perspectives. Planning authorities and practitioners should:

- Ensure stakeholder involvement in a transparent, well-defined process with a common and agreed-upon language and terminology.
- Ensure transparency and strengthen trust between different stakeholders engaged during the decision-making process and for knowledge exchange.
- Use proactive participatory mapping involving multiple stakeholders by investing the time and resources required to build the knowledge for an effective mapping exercise.
- Consider the diversity of understanding by using an adaptive and customised process in order to accommodate different perspectives, practices and interests.
- Ensure a balance or take corrective measures to safeguard minority or less powerful stakeholders.
- Ensure that the process takes account of the ecosystem services valued by the local stakeholders.

photo © Sandra Luque

Dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders, is crucial for a successful participatory processes. Time spent on engaging stakeholders at the beginning potentially saves time avoiding conflicts later.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/knowledge/ecosystem_assessment/index_en.htm

1.2.4. Address different impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services during planning processes (4.1.4, 4.1.6, 4.2.2., 4.2.5, 4.3.2, 5.4).

- National, sub-national and local authorities should:
 - › Consider mitigation and avoidance measures based on multiple spatial and temporal scales. For example, considerations of ecosystem services that are locally more rare or important or where there is a possibility for seasonal avoidance (e.g., avoiding breeding season).
 - › Implement pressure and intensity-based avoidance buffers that are specific to the wildlife of the area, e.g., noise mitigation measures during different offshore wind energy development stages (construction, operational and decommissioning stage).
 - › Promote an explicit analysis of the trade-offs (e.g., between biodiversity conservation and specific ecosystem services or among different categories of ecosystem services).
 - › Extend the transparency and replicability of environmental impact assessments and adoption of criteria and methods, and reduce the evaluation procedures based on subjective judgments.
 - › Ensure social equity of the impacts on ecosystem services and the associated mitigation measures (e.g., in terms of people's well-being and health) through the concept of no-worse-off.
 - › Incorporate synergies between biodiversity and ecosystem services within the mitigation hierarchy where they have complementary conservation targets.

1.2.6. Champion capacity building to ensure effective implementation and monitoring of the results (4.1.6, 4.3.5, 5.5).

- Planning authorities and institutions should invest time and resources to:
 - › Incorporate capacity building into institutional operational structures, including improvement of knowledge and communication.
 - › Institutionalise citizens' engagement to strengthen local and more sustainable dynamics where knowledgeable communities can act in the interests of biodiversity.
 - › Share knowledge opportunities; for example, the European Environment Agency (EEA) should collect information on best practices around Europe at the EU and national level and make the knowledge and database available to all the stakeholders.
- Practitioners and authorities should:
 - › Adopt more collaborative science practices with multiple stakeholders (e.g., citizen science).
 - › Encourage and support citizen science programmes as a means to engage and

1.2.5. Address connectivity and cumulative impacts during planning processes (4.1.3, 4.2.3, 4.3.3, 5.4).

- Stakeholder representatives and researchers
 - › Highlight connectivity hotspots based on different groups of species with varied dispersal capacities to provide an effective decision support tool for planning, including terrestrial, freshwater and marine realms that can be used to implement avoidance and mitigation measures.
- National authorities and land use planners should:
 - › Define procedures to address the cumulative effects in the planning process using an impact chain rationale as follows:
 - › Characterise the source(s) of pressure;
 - › Address the single/ multiple pressures exerted by the source(s);
 - › Address the impacts on biodiversity components (community, structure and function) and ecosystem services.
 - › Apply mapping and expert knowledge to link the impact chain rationale to effective avoidance and mitigation measures.
 - › Ensure that the current acceleration and simplification of administrative procedures to speed up renewable energy projects do not undermine a thorough assessment of cumulative effects.

educate citizens but also as a means of collecting extensive data for improved management and policymaking.

- › Disseminate the results of monitoring and evaluation activities to increase knowledge of what works and what does not.
- › Adopt a plurality of evaluation approaches in order to facilitate the understanding of assessment processes and results by different groups of stakeholders, including participatory assessment to build capacity, empower participants, sustain organisational learning, and improve the uptake of findings and understanding of data).
 - › For example, the co-creation of scenarios, such as the deliberative democracy process (Fontaine et al., 2014), a companion modelling approach (Sahraoui et al., 2021), probabilistic graphical modelling (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016), and reflexive monitoring.

1.3 Recommendations for researchers and educational/research institutions

- › Develop methods for ecosystem services assessment and areas with a high biodiversity value that are biome-specific (terrestrial, freshwater, coastal-marine) in order to take into account the bio-physical processes and socio-ecological conditions that determine ecosystem services demand and supply. Develop methods and create maps of ecosystem services and areas with a high biodiversity value in the marine space.
- › Conduct impact evaluations at different stages of the mitigation hierarchy (i.e., avoid, minimise, restore, compensate) to increase the evidence base of what works in practice. Impact evaluations need to follow best practices (e.g., have a Before-After Control-Intervention design) to be able to address cause-effect relationships and the effectiveness of the intervention.
- › Establish a common indicator framework for the evaluation of various Ecosystem Services using appropriate approaches (e.g., a combination of biophysical, economic, and sociocultural indicators), which also includes the assessment of ecosystem conditions.
- › Extend the traditional additive Cumulative Impact Assessment methods by including synergistic, antagonistic and dominant impact mechanisms that take account of the interactions from multiple pressures on biodiversity and ecosystem components.
- › Researchers should ensure stakeholder involvement is equitable in projects they conduct by including a wide range of stakeholders, especially minority and other often excluded groups, not just experts or easily reached groups. Adequate support should also be provided for their participation during all research stages. Unfortunately, while we see many reports and articles that advocate for working with stakeholders, few achieve a satisfactory level of involvement, most merely rely on expert representation. It is time that the scientific community puts the principles many promote into action and achieves truly equitable collaboration.
- › Develop capacity within educational/research institutions through, for example, adopting the service-learning approach (i.e. a process of a reflective and relational pedagogy that combines community or public service with structured opportunities for learning) and applying the existing expertise to enhance the good practice of mitigation hierarchy design and application.
- › Disseminate best practices and case studies of mitigation hierarchy application through knowledge and databases to relevant organisations by creating alliances with stakeholders in a learning-in-action approach.
- › Promote the uptake and effective implementation of the mitigation hierarchy by supporting the creation of a community of practice of researchers, planners and practitioners aimed at knowledge co-production and the sharing of best practices.

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Engaging stakeholders builds capacity for the future.

Background and objectives

2. Background and objectives

The Mitigation Hierarchy is the sequence of actions to anticipate and avoid adverse impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services (see the Glossary section for definitions). The avoid or prevent stage is the first and most important stage of the mitigation hierarchy in which developers anticipate adverse impacts on biodiversity before actions or decisions are taken. Action is then taken to prevent adverse impacts by considering different options in the project location, scale, layout, technology and phasing. Avoidance is often the easier, cheaper and more effective way than trying to restore a damaged habitat or offset elsewhere. The cost-effectiveness of this can only be realised by understanding the value of biodiversity and thus should be considered in the early stages of a project (Ekstrom et al., 2015).

However, our aim is to find out the extent in which the adherence to and implementation of the hierarchy is correctly applied and ecosystem services are considered and well documented. The activities should focus on the avoid and mitigation stages of the mitigation hierarchy (avoid-minimise-restore-compensate), so studies on restoration and compensation (e.g. biodiversity offsets) were excluded.

With this in mind, the French Biodiversity Agency put forward the following request to Eklipse (CfR.5/2020/2):

“How can ecosystem services be considered in plans, projects, programmes, policies and associated impact assessments with a particular focus on the avoid stage of the mitigation hierarchy?”

To answer this request, an Expert Working Group (EWG) on Mitigation hierarchy request was established, composed of members from different backgrounds (country distribution and career level) and research expertise (EU environmental laws and policies; landscape ecology and spatial planning; ecosystem services; environmental governance; evidence synthesis; marine, freshwater and terrestrial ecology; participation and stakeholder engagement; nature-based solutions).

The research had three main objectives:

1. To gather knowledge on how ecosystem services/natural capital as concepts foster the conservation and enhancement of biodiversity within planning processes in sectors that are likely to have a direct impact on biodiversity, e.g., infrastructure development, resource use and land use change.
2. To identify EU-wide cases and practices that actively consider and address the aspect of ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy, for example, in natural capital assessments, impact assessments of projects, plans, programmes, policies or similar processes.
3. To develop guidance on best practices and information on:
 - a. If and how the consideration and operationalisation of ecosystem services can be integrated into natural capital assessments, impact assessments, and policymaking processes to enhance biodiversity conservation as well as to understand the risks and potential ecosystem service trade-offs involved.
 - b. What kind of outcomes, impacts, challenges, solutions, etc., may occur when the ecosystem services concept is used in the natural capital assessments, impact assessments, mitigation hierarchy and similar processes?
 - c. The level of replicability/transferability of suggested/known tools/guidance/processes in other countries or regions that have been used successfully in the avoid stage.

This research aims to unveil whether land use planning and development in Europe is in line with the state of the art on biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services.

Methodological framework

3. Methodological framework

In order to address the research objectives presented in the introduction, the following steps were implemented:

- A systematic mapping as used to provide an overview of the available evidence and knowledge gaps present;
- An Applied Policy Delphi process for deliberative consultation, discussion, and feedback; and
- An analysis of results and conclusions based on the findings from the systematic mapping and the Applied Policy Delphi.

Figure 1. Presents the methodological framework by the Eklipse Expert Working Group to investigate how ecosystem services are incorporated into mitigation hierarchy policy.

3.1 Systematic mapping approach

The systematic mapping provided an overview of the distribution and amount of evidence that existed related to the objectives of the request. It helped to identify knowledge gaps in the literature for which further information was sought from the expert consultation process. The systematic mapping was conducted according to CEE guidelines (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018).

3.1.1. Question components

A modified PerSPECTiF framework (Booth et al., 2019) was used to outline the key question elements (Table 1). The question components were formulated based on the study questions and discussion with the requester about the details of the scope.

Table 1. Components of the study question

PER-SPECTIVE	SETTING	PHENOMENON OF INTEREST	ENVIRONMENT	EXPOSURE (PRESSURE)	DATE RANGE	FINDINGS
Global*	Impact assessments, natural capital assessments, and policymaking processes	Consideration and operationalisation of the ecosystem services concept to avoid and minimise impacts on ecosystem services and/ or biodiversity	Freshwater, marine and terrestrial ecosystems.	Infrastructure development, land use change and resource management	since 2000	Challenges and solutions for the use of ecosystem services concept, ecosystem services/biodiversity outcomes, trade-offs for people and between ecosystem services

*Although studies taking place anywhere in the world are included, the requester is especially interested in European cases and practices, reflected in the grey literature search.

3.1.2. Searches

3.1.2.1. Search terms and languages

A scoping exercise was conducted in the Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus. The search terms were defined in an iterative process of testing different terms and search strings (Annexe 1). The planning terms (#2) reflect the terms considered to have a potential impact on biodiversity. A list of relevant articles was used to test the comprehensiveness of the search (Annexe 2). The test list was compiled based on the suggestions from the EWG. The final search string (in Web of Science format) is:

#1 (avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR reduce OR impact OR foster OR enhanc* OR integrat*)

AND

#2 ("mitigation hierarchy" OR "land use planning" OR "management plan*" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*" OR "impact assessment" OR "green infrastructure" OR "blue infrastructure")

AND

#3 ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "biological diversity" OR "natural diversity" OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital").

The asterisk (*) at the end of a search term/word was used to accept any variant of a base term, whereas words or phrases within quotation marks were searched exactly as they appeared in the search string. A simplified search string was used where the full search string could not be used because of limitations of the search interface (e.g., in organisational websites). All search strings used were recorded (see Annexe 3).

Search languages were determined by mapping the language skills of the EWG and included English, French, German, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, Croatian, Finnish, Greek, Serbian and Swedish. The EWG acknowledges that not all European languages were covered and hence, the comprehensiveness of the search, especially grey literature, was not exhaustive (Figure 2). Organisational websites were searched in the primary language of the website in which it was published. In case the website included a unique publication section in any of the other search languages (not simply translations from the original publications), those were searched as well.

3.1.2.2. Bibliographic searches

Searches in the following bibliographic databases were conducted on 16.12.2021, and search alerts were set for articles published after the search date. Search alerts were discontinued on 28.2.2022 when full-text screening started.

Web of Science Core Collection

(<https://clarivate.com>):

- Topic search covering Science Citation Index Expanded (1945-present),
- Social Sciences Citation Index (1956-present),
- Arts & Humanities Citation Index (1975-present),
- Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Science (1990-present),
- Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Social Science & Humanities (1990-present),
- Emerging Sources Citation Index (2015-present).

Scopus; Title, abstract, and keyword search.

Lens (<https://www.lens.org>):

- Title, abstract,
- keyword or field of study.

3.1.2.3. Search engines

Google was used for Internet searches. The searches were conducted for each of the search languages in 'private mode' to avoid the influence of location and browsing history. The results were organised by relevance and checked until no more relevant results appeared (Livoreil et al., 2017). The cut-off was a hundred search records with no hits.

Search dates, number of hits and records searched were recorded (Annexe 1). Grey literature searches took place between 24.2-19.4.2022.

3.1.2.4. Organisational websites

Websites of international and national organisations in Europe (see Figure 2) were searched. These included, for example, websites of research organisations, ministries and government agencies, and environmental organisations identified by EWG members as potential organisations to have relevant literature on mitigation hierarchy. A full list of organisations and the search results are included in Annexe 4.

Figure 2. Map of the geographical areas covered by academic and grey literature searches.

3.1.2.5. Supplementary searches

A call for knowledge (Eklipse CfK.2/2020) was launched to compile and understand the type of knowledge available about the request, including case studies and practices on the use of the mitigation hierarchy. This call was published on the Eklipse website and widely distributed through networks and social media. Citation chasing was, in the end, not undertaken because of time constraints stemming from the relatively large number of articles screened.

3.1.2.6. Search record database

After the searches were completed, all references from academic databases were exported to Eppi Reviewer (Thomas et al., 2020), and duplicates were removed. An excel file was created for grey literature to record search results.

3.1.3. Article screening

Articles from the academic journals and grey literature were screened in two stages: 1) title and abstract and 2) full text. A single screening was conducted due to resource constraints. As screening involved multiple people, an alignment in screening decisions was established before screening at title and abstract commenced. A set of 20 articles were screened against inclusion criteria by all persons involved in the screening. Their inclusion/exclusion decisions were compared, and any discrepancies were discussed. After the first round, the inclusion criteria were clarified, and the process repeated with a new set of articles. Once the team was confident that their screening decisions were in agreement, the rest of the articles were divided among the screeners. If a screener was unsure during the screening whether to include or exclude an article, consultations were conducted with other team members and a joint decision was made. At the beginning of the full-text stage, five articles were screened together again to ensure alignment of screening decisions.

If articles shared the same study site (i.e., linked articles), they were screened together to avoid the inclusion of duplicate data, as recommended by Frampton et al. (2017). True duplicate studies were removed, and the rest were screened as a single unit to consider all available data pertinent to the study when the eligibility decision was made.

3.1.3.1. Eligibility criteria

The eligibility criteria were based on the study question components. Studies that fulfilled the following criteria were included:

Studies on freshwater, marine and terrestrial ecosystems anywhere in the world. This included studies on blue and green infrastructure as well.

- › Studies addressing the use of biodiversity and/or ecosystem services concepts in the context of impact assessments, spatial planning, and policy processes.
- › Studies addressing mitigation of impacts from grey infrastructure development, land use change and resource management on biodiversity and/or ecosystem services;
- › Studies on mitigation hierarchy needed to be focused on the avoidance and minimisation stages as per the request.
- › Both applied studies (i.e., real-world cases) and theoretical studies were included, as well as studies addressing governance frameworks, challenges and solutions.

3.1.3.2 Exclusion criteria

- › Literature and systematic reviews were excluded.
- › Studies on compensation and off-sets were excluded.
- › Studies, where impacts are minimised by restoring a habitat were also excluded.

photo © Sandra Luque

Our landscapes contain much more than what we see, and it is worth protecting.

3.1.4. Data extraction

At the beginning of data extraction, all persons involved in data extraction coded five articles together to ensure consistency and shared understanding. Any uncertainties during the data extraction phase were discussed among those involved in the systematic mapping, and a joint decision was made. The data was extracted using the following framework:

Metadata (data on study characteristics)

- › Source of the article.
- › Information on publication details (title, authors, publication year, DOI).
- › Type of publication (journal article, report, book, etc.).
- › Language.

Study attribute data

- › Ecosystem (Freshwater, marine and terrestrial).
- › Geographical location.
- › Scale of the study.
- › Exposure type (i.e., details on infrastructure development, land use change or resource management).
- › Applied or theoretical study.
- › Biodiversity or ecosystem services or both studied.
- › Studied ecosystem services.
 - › provisioning
 - › cultural
 - › regulating and maintenance
 - › ecosystem services disservice
- › Studied the level of biodiversity.
 - › landscape
 - › community
 - › species
 - › genes

- › Use of mitigation hierarchy (yes/no).
- › The stage of mitigation hierarchy (avoid or minimise).
- › Governance.
 - › legal framework for mitigation
 - › relevant government policies
 - › planning principles
- › Outcomes of the study.
 - › direct and indirect ES and/or biodiversity impacts (inclusive of loss of and damage to ecosystem services and/or biodiversity)
 - › trade-offs
 - › risks
 - › challenges
 - › solutions

During data extraction, additional study attributes emerged that were not mentioned in the original list of data to be extracted as published in the protocol. They were identified and added to the framework. The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICEcosystem services) V5.1 typology (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018) was used to categorise the ecosystem services into provisioning, cultural, regulation and maintenance categories (Figure 3). Only the upper-level categories were used. Where the authors of the paper had not assigned a category for the ecosystem services in question, one was assigned based on EWG's expert judgement during data extraction. Similarly, the stage of the mitigation hierarchy (avoid or minimise) was assigned during data extraction if not explicitly mentioned in the paper.

Figure 3. Ecosystem services classification based on Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018.

3.1.5. Data synthesis

A narrative synthesis describing the evidence base was produced. A primary output was the collation of a catalogue of cases where mitigation hierarchy had been used in practice. Various data visualisations, such as bubble maps, were used to illustrate the extent of the evidence related to the study objectives and knowledge gaps that exist.

3.2 Applied policy Delphi

The EWG conducted a deliberative email consultation involving an external expert panel using an Applied Policy Delphi technique to gain practical insights from experts involved in different aspects of the implementation of mitigation hierarchy or incorporating ecosystem services into land use planning. This was conducted in parallel to the systematic mapping process, where the result from the systematic mapping was used to help maximise the project outcomes, consequently:

- › Further evidence and relevant case studies were identified;
- › The process supported and built upon the EWG ideas and recommendations
- › Critical issues were discussed with the panellists that emerged from the systematic mapping, and differences in opinions were noted.
- › Feedback from the Applied Policy Delphi panel on the EWG synthesis of results was utilised to refine the draft recommendations for future policy and practice.

A panel of 11 experts from 9 countries was selected based on suggestions made by the EWG members via their networks and from further discussion within the group (Figure 4). The aim was to ensure appropriate representation of different types of experts (namely, practitioners, policymakers and researchers) and, as far as possible, different EU contexts and expertise, i.e., marine and terrestrial focus, based in different countries or with an international perspective and so on. We defined “experts” as people with on-the-ground experience in avoiding or mitigating biodiversity and/or ecosystem services impacts, e.g., consultants, resource managers, researchers, and policymakers, among others. A key goal was to ensure that all panellists have had some direct involvement in using the mitigation hierarchy or a related field, e.g., land use or marine spatial planning.

Operationally, the expert consultation in the Applied Policy Delphi process included the following steps, which were all conducted remotely through confidential email communication apart from the initial interviews and are summarised in figure 5:

3.2.1. Applied Policy Delphi round 0 Preliminary scoping interviews, part 1:

Preliminary individual interviews with experts were held remotely to explain the activities in detail, engage them in the process and engage key expertise for successive rounds. The central aim was to capture their initial standpoints with justification on the mitigation hierarchy and use of the avoid/minimise stage, highlighting barriers and opportunities.

Figure 4. Geographical representation of the Applied Policy Delphi panel.

3.2.2. Applied Policy Delphi round 0, Preliminary results, part 2:

The preliminary results of the scoping interviews were analysed using thematic analysis between January and March 2022. The interviews were transcribed and coded inductively with the support of a research assistant using NVivo software. The themes emerging from the interviews were identified by the EWG and systematised in the:

- › **Theme 1** Understanding of the mitigation hierarchy;
- › **Theme 2** Ecosystem services;
- › **Theme 3** Practical experience- delivery and lessons learned;
- › **Theme 4.** Strengths and Opportunities;
- › **Theme 5.** Weaknesses and Challenges;
- › **Theme 6.** Links with other policies and legal tools;
- › **Theme 7.** Links with tools and practices;
- › **Theme 8.** Future directions of the mitigation hierarchy.

These themes were used as headings for the outcomes of the Applied Policy Delphi process and combined with the outcomes from the systematic mapping process. The results are presented in the following section of this report. The results were compiled with initial systematic mapping results and presented to the experts. Areas of consensus and difference were highlighted in the research, and expert feedback was used to develop the priorities for questions for the first round;

DELPHI PROCESS PHASES

Figure 5. Applied Policy Delphi process phases.

3.2.3. Applied Policy Delphi round 1: Fusion of the systematic mapping and initial viewpoints of the Applied Policy Delphi Panel, part 1:

Here the Applied Policy Delphi process was used to complement and add value to the key findings from the systematic mapping and to identify the areas within which future guidance and recommendations were needed—for example, the key tools, governance frameworks and other drivers influencing success. A narrative was produced with questions

to express these outcomes. The first questionnaire included mostly open-ended questions aimed at capturing and discussing key critical issues associated with the conceptualisation and application of the mitigation hierarchy (avoid and minimise stages) as revealed through the systematic mapping and initial Applied Policy Delphi responses.

3.2.4. Applied Policy Delphi round 1: Responses and feedback, part 2:

The responses to the questions were analysed and shared with the EWG. The comments of the EWG were then integrated and fed back to the Applied Policy Delphi Panel.

3.2.5. Applied Policy Delphi Round 2: Towards guidance and policy recommendations, part 1:

Building on the work of the EWG, the draft final report, including the policy recommendations and guidance, was sent out for comment and feedback. The EWG used the feedback from the systematic mapping and previous Applied Policy Delphi rounds to set the recommendations.

3.2.6. Applied Policy Delphi Round 2: Collations and analysis, part 2:

The EWG then collated and analysed the responses to produce the final report.

3.2.7. Applied Policy Delphi round 3: Final feedback on the recommendations and guidance:

This final round involved feeding back the changes made by the EWG in response to the Applied Policy Delphi panel with a chance for a final set of responses. Focus was placed on the interplay between the Applied Policy Delphi panel and the EWG to maximise the expertise across the groups. Throughout the process, compliance with ethical issues was ensured following the procedures designed and agreed upon during the planning phases (Annexe 5).

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Plantation versus mixed forest, garden pest or food for birds, infestation or recycler.

Results

4. Results

This section presents the findings from the systematic mapping process followed by the Applied Policy Delphi Process outputs.

4.1. Systematic mapping

4.1.1. Overview of the evidence base

Figure 6 shows the number of articles included and/or excluded through the process. It resulted in 18 164 hits, of which 6356 were duplicates. After the screening, a total of 215 articles (peer-review and grey literature) were included in the narrative synthesis.

After that, and using an automatic document clustering (Figure 7), the included articles were divided into seven categories: land use planning, green infrastructure, marine spatial planning, water, environmental impact assessment, decision making, protected areas, and other categories, the environmental impact assessment was the largest category, followed by land-use planning.

Figure 6. Overview of the articles included and excluded as part of the systematic mapping using the ROSES form (Haddaway et al., 2017).

Figure 7. Overview of the topics of scientific articles included in the systematic mapping clustered by categories.

Figure 8. Overview of the coverage of the literature database included in the systematic mapping. The literature count is based on the number of studies covering a specific country or countries, including case studies on the local and regional levels.

The coverage of the literature database per type of biome is shown in Figure 8. The literature count is based on the number of studies covering a specific country, including case studies at the local and regional levels. The database has a good representation at the European level, with fewer studies in Eastern Europe. The largest number of terrestrial studies were conducted in France at the country level, whereas Spain had the largest number of freshwater-related studies. The largest number of coastal and marine studies identified covered the coastal areas of the United Kingdom, Denmark and Spain.

The literature database of terrestrial studies was classified into eight categories according to their ecosystem type: farmland, forest, grassland, mountain/alpine region, riparian landscapes, urban park, wetlands/peatlands, and multiple. Figure 9 shows the distribution of the literature on the different types of ecosystem categories per country. Farmland, forest and grasslands were the most studied categories compared to riparian landscapes and urban parks, which were the least researched.

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photo © Ian Storie

A multi species approach is needed to protect biodiversity.

Figure 9. Overview of the terrestrial literature database included in the systematic mapping by country.

4.1.2. Mitigation hierarchy as a concept

There were 45 papers that explicitly mentioned the mitigation hierarchy. The review demonstrates that the **mitigation hierarchy concept is relatively well-known** in the literature. Several papers referred to existing guidance documents (e.g., in Environmental Impact Assessments and Strategic Environmental Assessments) that clearly describe the different steps of the hierarchy and their application (Cullen 2006; Hayes et al., 2015). Even though there is an overall agreement about the usefulness of applying the mitigation hierarchy in relevant decision-making processes (Claireau et al., 2019; Jagerbrand and Bouroussis, 2021), the review of Environmental Impact Assessments conducted by Bigard et al. (2017) highlights the **avoidance stage is often**

disregarded, and measures “to avoid” are often actually measures “to reduce”. Furthermore, Barbe and Frascaria-Lacoste (2021) take a critical view of the mitigation hierarchy and question whether the policy goal of ‘No Net Loss of biodiversity’ should be based on a tool (i.e., mitigation hierarchy) that, at its core, is meant for, and largely used, only to reduce the harm caused by economic development, mainly from new projects.

The papers included both theoretical and applied studies as well as covered different outcomes (Figure 10). The majority of papers were on biodiversity, but ecosystem services were also included.

Figure 10. Papers on mitigation hierarchy. The bubble size denotes the number of papers. The green colour is for biodiversity, and the violet is for ecosystem services. An interactive form of this figure with links to the information on individual papers can be found here: https://eklipse.eu/wp-content/uploads/website_db/Request/Mitigation_hierarchy/Figure5_010622.html

4.1.3. Avoidance as a concept

The concept of avoidance requires “measures [are] taken to anticipate and prevent adverse impacts on biodiversity before actions or decisions are taken that could lead to such impacts” (CSBI 2015 in Hayes et al., 2015, p2).

Following Bull et al. (2022), avoidance can be defined as **action-based** (actions were taken to avoid impacts) or **outcome-based** (did the actions taken lead to avoided impacts). Mostly the focus is on direct impacts, but indirect impacts should also be kept in mind, especially leakage (impacts taking place elsewhere). As Bull et al. (2022, p374) point out, “it can never be assumed that avoiding environmental impacts within a certain jurisdiction will lead to their universal avoidance, in space and over time”. Also, avoidance is often associated with a change in land use, but cumulative impacts from ongoing land use, such as agriculture or forestry, may be large despite their typically small local footprint (Pappila, 2018). Furthermore, how we define and consider ‘adverse impacts’ and ‘significance’ can greatly influence the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy (Barbe and Frascaria-Lacoste 2021).

Barbe and Frascaria-Lacoste (2021, p4) argue that “the avoidance step does not always receive sufficient attention and leeway and does not always—as it should—raise the necessary questions about the choices (political, economic, etc.) that lead to new project development”. They further argue that “the mitigation hierarchy is insufficiently effective or relevant from the ecological perspective” (p4), a sentiment echoed by other authors. For example, Bigard (2017) maintains there is often no search for truly alternative options for avoidance in the early phases of development projects (which would allow an impact to be avoided), and there is an over-reliance on smaller revisions to reduce impacts.

A key issue is how impacts are avoided. In their earlier review, Phalan (2018) identified **four types of avoidance** measures: **project cancellation**, **spatial avoidance** (changing the location of a specific action), **temporal avoidance** (anticipating/differing that actions, activities do not take place during key seasons, e.g., breeding season), and **planning within site, i.e., design-based** impact avoidance (changing technology, operational methods, etc.). Furthermore, Tarabon et al. (2019a) highlight the importance of landscape-level land-use planning to ensure functional connectivity within the landscape. There is some evidence that spatial avoidance and technical measures are most commonly used to avoid impacts, whereas total avoidance of impacts, e.g., project cancellations, are less common (Hayes et al., 2015; Gelot and Bigard, 2021). This may be because “Often the EIA is undertaken when project feasibility and design plans are already advanced, and therefore the opportunity to intervene early to address avoidance strategies, including the identification of alternative site selection, is missed” (Hayes et al., 2015, p11). Enforcing this point, Bigard et al. (2020) recommend landscape scale as the appropriate scale for impact anticipation because it provides information on sites with high biodiversity values within that landscape that can be avoided before projects are approved.

4.1.4. Ecosystem services as a concept to foster the conservation of biodiversity within decision making

Considering ecosystem services under the mitigation hierarchy may further complicate the situation. For example, Ramel et al. (2020) asks if “the areas contributing most to preserve both biodiversity and ecosystem services coincide spatially, as suggested from work at the European scale?” as their results suggest that prioritising ecosystem services may “be disadvantageous to biodiversity”. Hence, while nature-based solutions may protect or enhance ecosystem services, they may not protect biodiversity (Seddon et al., 2020). This points to the importance of determining whether biodiversity impacts can be avoided (Préau et al., 2022), where biodiversity loss should be avoided, and then mapping the highest priority areas for protection at the landscape scale, as suggested by Bigard et al. (2020).

4.1.4.1. Trade-offs

A trade-off is ‘a situation where the use of one ecosystem services affects another ecosystem services and the benefits they supply’, but there are also situations where choices have not only to be made between ecosystem services but also between ecosystem services and non-ecosystem services. In general, **trade-offs are related to impacts that can be observed** (Gret-Regamey et al., 2008; Turkelboom et al., 2018), where choices may have real societal implications for stakeholders (Hayes et al., 2015).

Spatial planning deals with trade-offs between various stakeholders’ wishes and needs as part of planning, development and management of particular sites, landscapes, natural resources and/or biodiversity. To make ecosystem services trade-off research more relevant to spatial planning, the literature proposes different frameworks which **put stakeholders, their land-use/management choices, their impact on ecosystem services and responses at the centre of decision-making** (Turkelboom et al., 2018). In some cases, the analysis of ecosystem services trade-offs supports management choices that increase the delivery of other ecosystem services (Turkelboom et al., 2018; Di Marino et al., 2019). Within this framework, trade-off analysis supports sustainable urban planning (Di Marino et al., 2019), coastal benefits (Fontaine et al., 2014), and forest biodiversity (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016), among other applications.

It was pointed out in the literature that **integrating valuation approaches for ecosystem services helped to raise awareness of the societal benefits of green spaces** whilst also recognising the trade-offs between conflicting perspectives of stakeholders. Therefore, this aids the prioritisation of ecosystem

services (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016; Kovacs et al., 2016; Langemeyer et al., 2016a). Further, Fontaine et al. (2014) argue that preferences for iconic species present significant issues in constructing social values. It was also recognised that planners still struggle to incorporate green infrastructure and ecosystem services into land-use policy and planning practices due to the complex contexts – environmental, professional, cultural and political – aiming to maintain the status quo (Di Marino et al., 2019).

The literature shows that **provisioning ecosystem services were the most targeted trade-off, but regulating ecosystem services were the most impacted**. In addition, cultural ecosystem services are underrepresented because it is difficult to provide value for cultural ecosystem services that can be traded off against other ecosystem services, such as provisioning ecosystem services (Langemeyer et al., 2016). Ecosystem services are also often considered an aesthetic rather than a technical requirement (Khoshkar et al., 2020). Stakeholder characteristics, such as the degree of influence they have, the impacts they face, and their concerns, can partially explain their position and response in relation to trade-offs.

4.1.4.2. Trust and place attachment.

Trust is a major factor mentioned by Karrasch et al. (2014), where stakeholders were concerned about the impacts on their land use or possibly losing land. **Trust is necessary for implementing biodiversity strategies** that do not alienate people, for resolving conservation conflict (Kovacs et al., 2016), for decision-making processes and knowledge exchange between different stakeholders engaged. As Karrasch et al. (2014, p257) argue, place attachment needs to be considered, especially when stakeholders “were born and raised in the community and therefore had a strong sense of regional belonging and community cohesion”. Cerreta et al. (2021) also mentioned that trust was an important missing component in cultural ecosystem services evaluations.

Literature suggests it is important to **involve stakeholders in the process of evaluating ecosystem services to develop trust**, so results are not seen as “a black box” exercise. This would also help people to understand the value that nature provides them. It was stressed that this process had to be transparent enough for decision-makers without jeopardising scientific rigour, thus requiring time (Fontaine et al., 2014; Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016; Simeonova and van der Valk, 2016; Albert et al., 2021; Sahraoui et al., 2021).

4.1.5. Current use of mitigation hierarchy in decision making

4.1.5.1. Policies and regulations

Impact avoidance measures stem from both public and private sector governance instruments. Regulatory tools form the backbone of development and application of impact avoidance measures, e.g., protected areas or Environmental Impact Assessment. However, as Hayes et al. (2015) note, **there is no standardised framework for avoidance, and it varies considerably between countries**

(Table 2). In addition to regulations, there are voluntary instruments, such as third-party certification standards, financial loan requirements and corporate policies with requirements for avoidance, e.g., related to high biodiversity value habitats (Table 3).

Table 2. Examples of national and regional regulations and policies on avoidance of biodiversity impacts.

COUNTRY	LAW/POLICY	MITIGATION HIERARCHY	AVOIDANCE
United Kingdom	The National Planning Policy Framework of 2012 defines the national framework of planning policy for England with which administrative authorities issuing building permits must comply.	The mitigation hierarchy is defined as (1) Avoidance, (2) Reduction and (3) Compensation. Offsetting is not mandatory.	Paragraph 118 – When determining planning applications, local planning authorities should aim to conserve and enhance biodiversity by applying the following principles: if significant harm resulting from a development cannot be avoided (through locating on an alternative site with less harmful impacts), adequately mitigated, or, as a last resort, compensated for, then planning permission should be refused;
France	France adopted Decree n° 2011-2019, on 29 December 2011 on EIA, which will help making avoidance, reduction and compensation measures for environment more effective; those measures have to be described in the permit of the project, and their monitoring is compulsory.	The mitigation hierarchy is defined as (1) Avoidance, (2) Minimisation and (3) Compensation.	Avoidance is the same definition as BBOP: an avoidance measure is a measure which modifies a project or a public planification document in order to remove a negative impact that would occur.
Germany	The Eingriffsregelung (Impact Mitigation Regulation – IMR) requires the application of a mitigation hierarchy. This law is mandatory and precautionary, aiming to ensure “no net loss”.	The mitigation hierarchy is defined as (1) Avoidance, (2) Compensation and (3) Exemptions.	Under the provisions of Art. 15 (1) of the Federal Nature Conservation Law: The intervening party shall be obligated to refrain from any avoidable impairment of nature and landscape. The increased flexibility of IMR implementation does not impair the absolute priority of avoidance and minimisation. This means that given the option between avoidance and minimisation of the impacts on the one hand and compensation on the other, the project proponent must choose avoidance and minimisation of impacts.

COUNTRY	LAW/POLICY	MITIGATION HIERARCHY	AVOIDANCE
EU	Habitats Directive, Management of Natura 2000 sites for EU Member States.	The EIA Directive defines mitigation as avoid, reduce and, if possible, remedy significant adverse effects.	Habitats Directive Article 6.1 Avoid damaging activities that could significantly disturb these species or deteriorate the habitats of the protected species or habitat types.
	The EIA Directive Applies to a wide range of defined public and private projects, which are defined in Annexes I (Mandatory EIA) and II (Discretion of Member States).		The EIA Directive Should contribute to avoiding any deterioration in the quality of the environment and any net loss of biodiversity, in accordance with the Union's commitments in the context of the Convention and the objectives and actions of the Union Biodiversity Strategy up to 2020 laid down in the Commission Communication of 3 May 2011 entitled 'Our life insurance, our natural capital: an EU biodiversity strategy to 2020'.
	SEA Directive. SEA Directive must be prepared or adopted by an authority (at national, regional or local level) and be required by legislative, regulatory or administrative provisions.		
Australia	The Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999 (EPBC Act) is the Australian Government's principal piece of environmental legislation. One of the legislations objectives is to provide a streamlined national environmental assessment and approvals process.	With respect to the different stages of the mitigation hierarchy, the focus of EPBC Act supporting policy and guidance is on offset design and implementation. Avoidance and mitigation measures are described as primary strategies for managing significant impacts. Offsets will not be considered until all	Avoidance of impacts on protected matters may be achieved through comprehensive planning and suitable site selection, for example by changing the route of an access road to avoid an endangered ecological community.

Source Hayes et al., 2015

Table 3. Examples of voluntary tools to implement the avoidance stage of the mitigation hierarchy (source Phalan et al. 2018).

	STANDARD OR LAW	ACTIONS				CRITERIA FOR MOVING PAST AVOIDANCE STAGE			
		Consult with stakeholders	Assess environmental and social impacts	Consider cumulative impacts	Implement long-term monitoring	No viable lower-impact alternative	Overriding public interest	No net impact on critical biodiversity features	Compliance with the law
Standards and guidance	Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme: Standard on Biodiversity Offsets (2012)	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓
	Cross Sector Biodiversity Initiative: A cross-sector guide for implementing the Mitigation Hierarchy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development: Performance Requirement 6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	International Finance Corporation: Performance Standard 6*	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓
	World Bank: proposed Environmental and Social Standard 6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Legislation	Australia: Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act,		✓		(✓)	✓		✓	✓
	British Columbia (Canada): Policy for Mitigating Impacts on Environmental Values	(✓)	✓	✓	(✓)	✓			✓
	European Union: Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, EIA Directive	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
	United Kingdom: National Planning Policy Framework 2012	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓

*Requirements for consultation and impact assessment are established in IFC Performance Standard 1

In the majority of European countries, the European Union (EU) plays an important role in setting policy and regulatory frameworks. General EU policies linked to impact avoidance measures include: the EU Green Deal (2019), the CAP (Common Agricultural Policy)(2021), the EU Soil Strategy 2030 (2021), the EU taxonomy (2020), the EU Adaptation Strategy (2021), the EU Action Plan for disaster risk reduction (2016), and the EU biodiversity strategy (2010 and 2020).

4.1.5.2. Impact avoidance measures in EU policies and regulations related to biodiversity

Several EU policies and regulations have an impact on biodiversity (Figure 11). The EU biodiversity strategy for 2030, adopted in 2020 (EU, 2020), is a long-term plan to protect nature and reverse ecosystem degradation by prioritising biodiversity throughout the other EU policies. It represents a core part of the EU Green Deal and will also support green recovery after the pandemic. It distinguishes itself from the previous Communication of 2011 by establishing a Trans-European Nature Network of protected areas covering 30% of EU land and seas, an EU Nature Restoration Plan with binding targets and a set of measures enabling a 'transformative change' including better tracking, knowledge base and financing.

photos © Sini Savilaakso

Will the coming decade see success in protecting valuable habitats, such as biodiversity-rich forests and ancient woodlands?

Source European Commission

Figure 11. EU policies and initiatives (on the left) shape EU-level legislation (on the right) that impacts biodiversity. In addition, global climate change and biodiversity policies (the purple circles) influence biodiversity conservation. The Marine Directive includes both the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD)

At the regulation level, **avoidance is strongly embedded in the Birds and Habitats Directives** (EU-DG Environment, 2014) that focus on species and habitats in need of protection. The two directives require the Member States to do more to prevent further deterioration of these species and habitat types. They must also undertake positive management measures to ensure populations are maintained or restored. According to Article 6, par. 2 of the Habitats Directive: “Member States shall take appropriate steps to avoid, in the special areas of conservation, the deterioration of natural habitats and the habitats of species as well as disturbance of the species for which the areas have been designated, in so far as such disturbance could be significant in relation to the objectives of this Directive.”

To help the application of Article 6, the Commission issued various methodological guidance documents, such as ‘Managing Natura 2000 sites’ (EU-DG Environment, 2021). The guidance explicitly states that the term ‘avoid’ refers to “the **anticipatory nature of the measures** to be taken. It is not acceptable to wait until deterioration or disturbances occur before taking measures” (p. 25). Furthermore, Article 6(2) specifies that appropriate avoidance steps must be taken ‘in so far as such disturbance could be significant in relation to the objectives of this Directive’. Therefore, the disturbance in question has to be relevant to (i.e., have an impact on) the conservation status of the species in relation to the objectives of the Directive.

Similarly, in 2020, the EU Commission issued guidance on wind energy developments and EU nature legislation (EU-DG Environment, 2020) that explicitly addressed the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy and, namely, the avoidance

stage: “A spatial plan should ideally identify categories of locations suitable for wind energy development, listed in order of priority ranging from locations of low-ecological-risk deployment (in terms of the objectives of the Nature Directives) to locations of high-ecological-risk deployment. In sites with exceptionally high biodiversity values, this could even lead to defining exclusion zones” (p.44).

The guidance further states: “The ‘mitigation hierarchy’ applies, which means that measures to avoid negative effects in the first place must be considered and implemented before measures to reduce negative effects. It is also **good practice to apply these measures at the source before considering measures for the receptor**. The best way to minimise negative effects on EU-protected habitats and species is to locate projects away from vulnerable habitats and species (a practice known as ‘macro-siting’). This can best be achieved through **strategic planning at the administrative, regional, national or even international level**, in particular through the maritime spatial plans drawn up under the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive. Cooperation between the Member States and with countries outside the EU is also required when developing maritime spatial plans.”

4.1.5.3. Impact avoidance measures and land-use planning

A review of national and international policies across eight different countries showed that the mitigation hierarchy is often associated with EIA requirements both at the International and national level despite some variations on the stages (Hayes et al., 2015). Avoidance stated as primary stage might include some options like: alternative site selection, comprehensive planning, areas of exclusion, avoiding impacts on species, habitats, nature, landscapes or the environment, using the precautionary principle and NNL. For this reason, it has been observed that avoidance is inconsistently defined and applied as a concept in land use regulations (Hayes et al., 2015).

With special regard to the EU, the mitigation hierarchy is not directly defined within the Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (2001/42/CE).

However, the directive refers to measures to prevent, reduce and, if possible, offset significant adverse effects on the environment of implementing the plan or programme (see Annex I, lett. G) as information to be provided in the Environmental Report (art. 5). Also, a clear definition of avoidance is not provided in the EIA Directive but the characteristics and criteria to identify significant adverse effects can be found in Annex II. In 2011, the European Parliament further stressed the **need to strengthen the EIA Directive (2001/42/CE)** for a more rigorous interpretation of its objectives. The aim was to achieve No Net Loss and, where possible, biodiversity gains. In addition, it was stressed that specific requirements were needed for the ongoing monitoring of biodiversity impacts of projects and the effectiveness of mitigation measures, including appropriate provisions to access information for enforcement.

Concerning the latter point, an example from Bulgaria highlights that despite a legal requirement for stakeholder consultation in land use design and environmental impact assessments, there were still implementation problems. While public hearings are commonly used to hear stakeholder opinions, in practice, it is often merely a formality (Simeonova and van der Valk, 2016). This is in line with the findings of Tillemann et al. (2021) in Estonia, who conclude that **it is not only legislative requirements**

that determine the efficiency of ecological network planning and implementation but a rather effective implementation. Other examples from practice, such as the bottom-up initiative for the development of the disused Airport Tempelhof, Germany, confirm that local stakeholders' values' are not always properly accounted for in planning processes (Langemeyer et al., 2016a).

It must be pointed out that the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy through planning laws relies on **consistent decision-making between various governance levels.** This is hard to achieve, considering that land use planning is a separate

Consistent application of land use regulations is needed to protect biodiversity.

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process from planning and conserving natural areas (Toivonen et al., 2021), and the most significant policy gaps notably concern the treatment of unavoidable residual impacts on biodiversity outside Natura 2000 sites (Pilgrim, 2013; van Teeffelen, 2014; Quétier, 2015; Schulp et al., 2016). Finland provides a good example of a collaborative process involving different levels. It has 18 Regional Councils with the remit to guide municipal planning processes by reconciling international, national, and regional rules and regulations with local interests (Toivonen et al., 2021). Conversely, in Sweden, municipalities have the main responsibility

for spatial planning, thus, decisions taking into account ecosystem services and biodiversity can be taken at the local level generating multiple-level benefits (Khoshkar et al. 2020).

Establishing a sufficient scientific base for avoiding the negative impacts of projects is often not ensured under the current legal framework. Nevertheless, the practice shows this does not hamper project approval, in spite of the precautionary principle. Indeed: "In most cases, the evidence base was sufficient to enable developers and decision-makers to comply with the Nature Directives, but there were knowledge gaps, which posed a challenge for developers and decision-makers when evaluating the impact of energy projects" (Moreira, 2019, p136). A clear obstacle to achieving an accurate basis for decision-making is the long administrative procedures required, which increases developers' administrative costs (Kyriazi et al., 2016).

4.1.5.4. Impact avoidance measures and marine spatial planning

In the most important EU-level Directives for marine biomes (EU, 2008), **the concept of mitigation hierarchy is not explicitly mentioned**. Instead, it refers to mitigation or mitigation measures of certain phenomena to be tackled through marine spatial planning by the Member States. In particular, the Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSP) 2014 (2014/89/EU) defines in Article 13 that “...*healthy marine ecosystems and their multiple services, if integrated in planning decisions, can deliver substantial benefits in terms of food production, recreation and tourism, climate change mitigation and adaptation, shoreline dynamics control and disaster prevention.*” Article 14 of the Directive specifies that Member States should use an ecosystem-based approach (EBA) to promote sustainable use of marine resources and “...*that the collective pressure of all activities is kept within levels compatible with the achievement of good environmental status (GES)*”..., as described within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; 2008/56/EC). Article 14 of the MSP Directive identifies “...*Member States should take into account the precautionary principle and the principle that preventive action should be taken*”. Article 30 defines that the “*Member State... should take appropriate ad-hoc measures with the aim of continuing to pursue the environmental targets, preventing further deterioration in the status of the marine waters affected and mitigating the adverse impact within the marine region or subregion concerned.*”

Harnessing cultural ecosystem services has the potential to lead to protective actions to conserve valued landscapes.

Photo © Sini Savilaakso

4.1.6. Use of ecosystem services concept and mitigation hierarchy

4.1.6.1. Impacts

The systematic mapping showed the **diversity of frameworks for impact assessment**; for example: the shellfish reef-based management framework focused on marine spatial planning (Cobacho et al., 2020), conservation priority networks for vulnerable marine ecosystems and the systematic conservation plan (Combes et al., 2021), biodiversity impact assessments (Geneletti, 2003), Strategic Environmental Assessment and Environmental Impact Assessment (Honrado et al., 2013). Furthermore, there is the administrative and financial incentive scheme, the high nature value area, which proved an important factor for mitigating conflict (Kovacs et al., 2016). Similar results were obtained in the analysis of the effectiveness of the Cumulative Effects Assessment carried out by Farella et al. (2021)

However, ecosystem services benefits are often overlooked due to many factors, including a lack of integration of local stakeholders into ecosystem services valuation processes (Fontaine et al., 2014; Karrasch, 2014; Kovacs, 2016) and an underestimation by businesses of the value of natural capital, especially of intangible benefits (Cambridge Conservation Initiative 2020;

Gontier, 2007; Iberdrola, 2019). Landowners also overlook ecosystem services due to a lack of incentives when benefits accrue to others (Eyvindson, 2018; Iberdrola, 2019; Salata, 2020). Honrado et al. (2013), in an analysis of Strategic Environmental Assessments and Environmental Impact Assessment practices, underline the fact that **benefits from ecosystem services are being overlooked** in both instruments, and they are often not explicitly considered. Honrado et al. (2013) propose testing the ecosystem services-based framework for environmental assessment to remedy the situation.

Three types of approaches are put forward characterising the inclusion of biodiversity in Environmental Impact Assessments (Gontier et al., 2006): (a) an approach focused on **single sites or a single biodiversity element** with no general overview, (b) a functional and dynamic **ecosystem approach** and (c) a **habitat suitability approach** based on processes.

In relation to the first approach, there are different single-site impacts. Gontier et al. (2006) used modelling methods for the prediction of habitat suitability for the lesser spotted woodpecker. These authors demonstrate that the analysis of the habitat suitability, impact analysis, or potential distribution of one species is *“not an assessment of biodiversity, but it can still provide valuable information on potential impacts on the ecological value of an area”* (Gontier et al., 2006, p455).

For the second - a functional and dynamic ecosystem approach - several studies reinforce ecological importance by identifying and mapping high-priority areas for protection and superimposing them onto an urban development plan, thereby indicating avoidance in terms of landscape (e.g. Geneletti, 2003; Azzellino et al., 2013; Coppola et al., 2019; Bigard et al., 2020).

The third approach takes participatory processes into consideration. Potential benefits of the impact assessment process include tools to generate new ideas, new forms of knowledge co-production and self-reflexivity, and mutual learning about the values and interests of other stakeholders anchored in a learning-by-doing process (Kovacs et al., 2016).

The application of the mitigation hierarchy and ecosystem services within impacts assessment provides an **opportunity to identify conflicts and synergies** between human actions and ecosystems, to establish dialogue and negotiation processes, to enhance gains for beneficiaries and avoid losers, as well as to explore long term benefits for which the strategic level of discussion is appropriate (Hornado et al., 2013). Although in many papers, the avoidance stage is not mentioned explicitly, the evaluation process infers it. The use of evidence within the impact framework can either indicate solutions for the avoidance step or assess whether this step has been adequately achieved.

4.1.6.2. Risks and Challenges

There are many risks and challenges to implementing biodiversity protection measures highlighted by the systematic mapping analysis. These range from a lack of institutional capacity to the complexity of managing landscapes for biodiversity. The notion of risk and challenges within the mitigation hierarchy has several dimensions relating to **how the mitigation hierarchy can contribute to the reduction of adverse environmental effects** on biodiversity/ecosystem services; and **how adaptations of the mitigation hierarchy framework across scales, methods and stakeholder groups have been misused**. In the following sections, the most important risks and challenges are addressed.

Building capacity involves multiple stakeholders in a collaborative learning process.

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Institutional capacity

There are a **number of constraints on the institutional capacity of authorities and local organisations**, particularly in resourceconstrained municipalities, which are unable to hire personnel with the necessary knowledge (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016; Di Marino et al., 2019; Khoshkar, 2020). Thus, understanding Green Infrastructure and ecosystem services for implementation in planning at the local level is variable (Hayes et al., 2015; Lange-meyer et al., 2016b; Di Marino et al., 2019). Even at the governmental level, there is a lack of knowledge, for example, of the marine

environments required for projects, such as wildlife protection, offshore renewable energies or fracking (Moreira, 2019).

Loss of highly motivated personnel further compromises capacity (Madsen et al., 2017). Significant capacity building is therefore needed, including an increase in organisations' social and collective capacity (Simeonova and van der Valk, 2016; Madsen et al., 2017; Mazziotta et al., 2017). These issues are particularly acute in post-socialist countries, where unpredictable, hierarchical and fragmented structures are key concerns (Simeonova and van der Valk, 2016; Logmani et al., 2017; Simeonova et al., 2019). **Capacity building, though, requires significant investments of time** and can be technically demanding (Heinonen, 2019; Albert et al., 2021), which is often lacking in busy planning departments (Madsen et al., 2017; Di Marino et al., 2019).

Capacity issues in the private sector may also exist. Some lack the relevant knowledge of how their activities impact the environment, especially on the ecosystem services and biodiversity impacts that local communities depend on. Consequently, their perception of risks to environmental resources may differ, leading to uncertain costs and benefits to business and society, as well as the potential for conflicts (Mazziotta et al., 2017; Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020; Markantonatou et al., 2021).

Management complexity

Literature suggests that two of the most widely used decision-support tools to inform urban land-use planning are **Environmental Impact Assessment**

and **Cost-Benefit Analysis**

(CBA). These have played an important role in the practical integration of environmental concerns into urban land-use planning. However, the Environmental Impact Assessment has faced much criticism due to a weak structure, built upon economic and legal values, far removed from ecology (Bigard et al., 2017; Barbe & Frascaria-Lacoste, 2021). Concerns that **economic interests were prioritised over conservation** measures were raised in the agricultural sectors (Kovacs et al., 2016; Lakner et al., 2020), Blue Growth in the marine sectors (Markantonatou et al., 2021) and the timber sector (Mazziotta et al., 2017). Combes et al. (2021), however, state that

socioeconomic costs are essential to be considered and minimised, especially where they overlap with conservation areas. **Management choices must take into account different scenarios.** Scenario-based frameworks, though, face a limited capacity in integrating ecosystem services and associated values, particularly with unmeasurable, non-market services, which can be highly site-specific and may change over time (Gret-Regamey et al., 2008; Fontaine et al., 2014; Langemeyer et al., 2016b; Leone and Zoppi, 2019; Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020; Cobacho et al., 2020). They also often make strong assumptions of stable human preferences for a specific ecosystem service at stake, therefore, this adds a degree of uncertainty to the scenario (Fontaine 2014). Temporality is also a particular issue for the long-term management of areas where avoidance has been applied and is dependent on the tenure of the system put in place, especially since post-monitoring is rarely well-

supervised, resulting in depreciating biodiversity values (Barbe & Frascaria-Lacoste 2021; Hayes 2015). **Lack of transparency and replicability** of environmental impact assessments is an additional common shortcoming causing inconsistencies across countries and evaluation procedures largely based on subjective judgments (Pöder, 2006). The methodological framework set by standards ISO 14001 and ISO 14004 gives only general principles for environmental impact assessments. Moreover, even in countries where the environmental impact assessment is quite advanced, there are still unanswered questions, especially concerning cumulative effects and the monitoring of environmental effects (Weiland, 2010).

How "green" are our green landscapes?

photo © Sandra Luque

Cumulative impact assessments, therefore, are useful instruments that can help address and locate mitigation and avoidance measures, but they need to be provided at an adequate landscape scale. This is because apparent small-scale impacts or losses may result in significant impacts at the national scale (Hayes 2015). Before and after analyses in Environmental Impact Assessment studies are also essential at a systematic level (Claireau et al., 2019).

Scale

Ecosystems are not static systems, nor are they bounded by administrative boundaries posing problems for their management when broader-scale decisions

are needed (Kurttila et al., 2002; Gontier, 2007; Gret-Regamey et al., 2008; Fichera et al., 2015; Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016; Langemeyer et al., 2016b; Di Marino et al., 2019; Barbe & Frascaria-Lacoste, 2021). For example, basin-scale marine spatial planning is needed to mitigate against increasing impacts from the fishing and mining sectors (Azzellino 2013; Combes 2021).

Landscape effects impact biodiversity where species dispersal characteristics are influenced by a particular landscape matrix (Muratet et al., 2007; Tarabon et al., 2019b; Sahraoui et al., 2021). For example, lighting, provided for safety reasons, impacts light-sensitive species affecting circadian rhythms, predation, feeding and reproduction (Voigt et al., 2018; Jagerbrand and Bouroussis, 2021). Some studies found that the **current mitigation measures at the species level are inadequately implemented or have never been proven to be effective** (Delbaere et al., 2009; Claireau et al., 2019; Tarabon et al.,

2019a). An example is the potential biodiversity loss in the time taken to construct wildlife corridors or overpasses (Tarabon 2019a).

Mejia et al. (2015) and Markantonatou et al. (2021) highlight the **need for an ecosystem-based approach in resource management** to improve the decision-making process. In addition, Toivonen et al. (2021) argues for increasing the size of nature protection areas as 70% of biodiversity currently lies outside these areas. However, as Markantonataou (2021) points out, stakeholders prefer smaller protection zones, even though decision-makers prefer larger areas for administrative reasons.

Multi-stakeholder collaboration

Policies can add to the uncertainty and environmental risks to society. The absence of any social dimension that recognises the competing values of stakeholder groups creates a barrier to effectively avoiding impacts (Hayes et al., 2015). However, **participation is sometimes limited to consultation and not collaboration**, which hampers stakeholder engagement (Simeonova & van der Valk 2016). The ecological network concept can be successfully implemented into planning documents only with an effective stakeholder network and an adequate basis for information across all levels of governance (Tillemann et al., 2021).

Formal and informal multi-layered governance structures of urban green spaces determine their management and the importance of ecosystem services in land-use planning and participatory decision-making. **Formal participatory measures in land-use governance tend to be ineffective** due to insufficient information flows within multi-level governance structures, lack of administrative coordination between upper governance levels and local and regional levels, insufficient administrative capacity and exclusion of certain stakeholders from the planning phase (e.g., NGOs, local association, social movements, citizens organised individually and collectively). The **ecosystem services concept, therefore, is not fully acknowledged in spatial planning** (Lai et al., 2017; Di Marino et al., 2019) even though the socio-spatial context is essential for planning frameworks (Albert et al., 2021). The complexity inherent within ecosystems also presents a significant barrier to implementation in land-use planning, where **assessments tend to focus on the flow of benefits**

to people and so fail to recognise the current and future role of biodiversity (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016; Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020). Limitations to the evaluation criteria chosen can occur as **citizens are usually concerned with short-term benefits, whereas the experts view the long-term ones** (Langemeyer et al., 2016a). Therefore, new instruments and forms of science-practice collaboration in planning processes are needed (Gret-Regamey et al., 2008; Bigard et al., 2020; Sahraoui et al., 2021).

Data Quality

Spatial quality of the data, its comprehensiveness and costs are important in a given territory to ensure that local characteristics are taken into consideration (Borgström and Kistenkas, 2014; Barbosa et al., 2019; Bigard et al., 2020). Failing to do so may lead to negative outcomes, particularly when a territory contains multiple landowners with varying interests (Kurttila et al., 2002; Albert et al., 2021). For example, forests may lose their functionality if they become reduced in size and become fragmented, but strategies need to also address the unequal impacts on landowners, ensuring equitable application (Kurttila et al., 2002; Tarabon et al., 2019a, b).

Data sets created from multiple classification systems, varying sources and resolutions never

present an accurate picture at a point in time (Koschke et al., 2013). They may fail to account for the temporal nature of a territory, particularly for migratory species (Kovacs et al., 2016; Madsen et al., 2017; Bigard et al., 2020), and this is further compounded by low-resolution land maps reflecting unbalanced priorities that overlook the ecological complexity (Casalegno et al., 2014; Di Marino et al., 2019).

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Institutionalising participatory processes in a meaningful process means ensuring information flows between stakeholders.

4.1.6.3. Solutions

It is argued in the literature that **scenarios, monitoring and evaluation are crucial** for exploring the impacts of time, future challenges, space and trends on current situations (Fontaine et al., 2014; Albert et al., 2021). Various methods were suggested for the co-creation of the scenarios, such as a deliberative democracy process (Fontaine et al., 2014), a companion modelling approach (Sahraoui et al., 2021), probabilistic graphical modelling (Gonzalez-Redin et al., 2016), and reflexive monitoring.

Involving stakeholders in a well-defined process to incorporate their views and perceptions is important in addressing conflicts related to conservation of protected species (Kovacs et al., 2016). However, different understandings between disciplines and sectors require an adaptive process, as effective avoidance strategies can only emerge through cross-sectoral and multi-stakeholder collaboration (Karrasch et al., 2014; Hayes et al., 2015; Madsen et al., 2017; Sahraoui et al., 2021). The environmental, social and economic issues intertwined in ecosystem services does not guarantee adequate inclusion of social impacts in evaluation schemes. Therefore, a common vocabulary between disciplines and stakeholders is needed, as well as conflict resolution between productionist and conservation viewpoints (Sheate et al., 2008; Karrasch et al., 2014; Logmani et al., 2017; Brignon et al., 2022).

Understanding the complexity of landscapes and the multiple values held by experts and stakeholders helps identify potential pathways forward to protect biodiversity.

photo © Sandra Luque

Long-term maintenance is needed in areas where avoidance has been applied and therefore requires national legislation to ensure its continuity. Since voluntary standards are insufficient to ensure future support and investments avoidance measures are usually put in place (Hayes et al., 2015).

Nature-based solutions emerged in the literature as an opportunity to address societal challenges using ecological processes. In most cases, nature-based solutions are applying new solutions to address existing problems, which helps protect existing ecosystem services and biodiversity (Albert et al., 2021).

Literature suggests that the inclusion of the **ecosystem services-based approach in coastal ecosystem** management has so far been largely absent (Karrasch et al., 2014), although it could be a potential solution for inclusive management. The Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) can bridge

ecosystem services and policy processes. However, Langemeyer et al. (2016a, p54) suggests it is not the “silver bullet” as there are limitations where there are multiple levels of ecosystem services supply and demand. For example, there are difficulties in defining problems and dealing with several issues and the potential risk of marginalisation of “*minority objectives*” (Langemeyer et al. 2016a, p55).

4.2 Applied Policy Delphi process

4.2.1. Mitigation hierarchy as a concept

Generally, there was a **range of different understandings of the concept** evident. For some, the mitigation hierarchy was seen as part of a process leading toward sustainability and biodiversity

protection. However, only four panellists explicitly mentioned that the mitigation hierarchy is mainly focused on initiatives to protect ecosystems or measures linked to pressures (pollution, spatial planning, climate change), with panellist 7 stating, “*mitigation hierarchy is kind of connected, in my opinion with this DPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, States, Impacts, Responses) framework*”. Most panellists agreed there are four aspects to the mitigation hierarchy, “*avoidance, minimisation, restoration and offsetting*”, where the first two stages fall into preventative actions. They agreed that the avoidance stage is “*the very first phase that we should have, with the present ideas about*

transition” [Panellist 1]. However, Panellist 1 also suggested that the mitigation hierarchy should have five stages, with “*enhance*” as the first stage.

All panellists had expertise in using the general principles of the mitigation hierarchy; however, **most use varying terms for mitigation measures in practice**. It was perceived that the mitigation hierarchy “*is implicit rather than explicit*” and focused on “*quantitative hierarchy (e.g., metrics, indicators for biodiversity), not a qualitative framework or a part of Environmental Impact Assessment*” [Panellist 3]. Despite the varying definitions of the mitigation hierarchy, panellists considered it a useful tool for practical issues or as part of a broader approach to environmental management, e.g., spatial planning or ecosystem-based management. It was stressed that the mitigation hierarchy is a valuable tool for biodiversity protection, among others, due to aspects

of stakeholder involvement and transparency—which are embedded in the holistic approach and supported by the precautionary principle.

4.2.2 Ecosystem services as a concept to foster the conservation of biodiversity within planning processes

One of the tasks of this project is to see if the ecosystem services concept could be useful to the application of the mitigation hierarchy. During the interviews, a general consensus emerged that **including ecosystem services could indeed be beneficial**, although at least one panellist expressed strong disagreement with including ecosystem services into the mitigation hierarchy: *“having people external to the technical discussion, you want to make sure that incorporating ecosystem services into the mitigation hierarchy isn’t in the end of shutting these people out - it’s hard enough to train a judge on what a species is, what the habitat of that species is, and on what basis it was determined to be protected and therefore has this and that legal provision. But if you start mixing in much more fuzzy concepts, and the problem with ecosystem services is that it’s much more fuzzy than ‘is this a frog, not a frog’? You might be generating confusion and lots of obstacles for other people – non-technical people to be involved”* [Panellist 2].

Several panellists highlighted that the concept helps to translate the biophysical environment into the value they bring to people. This **process of translating the values** helps in understanding how the site is used by stakeholders. However, panellist 2 pointed out that *“you’re assuming that some kind of expert is able to describe and document the ecosystem services, and in this way somehow speaks on behalf of the people who use or depend on those ecosystems and so you’re creating a barrier in fact, rather than an enabling environment for people to voice their concerns - to make sure that you don’t replace a much more effective system...with something that gives power to experts so that they tell the people what are ecosystem services”*. It also allows the use of different types of methods and indicators (that may include, for example, the analysis of ecosystem conditions and ecosystem accounting). This **plurality of evaluation approaches offers a great advantage** *“because for some groups of people it’s very good to*

see numbers, for other people it’s very good to have data presented qualitatively in storylines” [Panellist 6], and for some, it will be combining both together.

Another broadly agreed-upon advantage of using the ecosystem services concept is the generation of spatially-explicit analysis of the distribution of ecosystem services. **Ecosystem services maps are helpful to identify irreplaceable areas** where impact avoidance should be enforced but also to contribute to the identification of pragmatic solutions for developments that need to go somewhere, and for proposing suitable offsetting measures.

Some panellists, however, shared concerns about how the ecosystem services concept is applied in

Stakeholders and members of the SMT of Thau Region (<https://www.smbt.fr/>) France, workshop to map ES.

photo © Sandra Luque

impact assessment and mitigation practices. The first concern relates to the **separation of ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation**, which is not consistent with the idea that biodiversity is essential to support all ecosystem services. In the words of Panellist 1, *“the ecosystem services component for me it’s obviously an all-encompassing thing, not detaching conservation from sustainable use aspects. (...) You have to process this stuff from an integrated perspective. (...). Conservation and sustainable use of ecosystem services is something you have to address in one topic and not split up”*. However, Panellist 8 highlighted that in Estonia, conservation issues are rooted in legislation, but

ecosystem services only have implicit backing and not legal backing in decision-making.

A second concern, shared by two panellists, is the **excessive focus on the direct benefits** that people get from the natural environment and on associated cost-benefit analyses: *“Because a lot of people when they think ecosystem services, they think cost-benefit analysis and looking at the economic value from an ecosystem service and somehow thinking that decisions are made on a harmful project on the basis of rigorous cost-benefit analysis, which is not true”* [Panellist 2].

Individual panellists also identified a few critical points that need to be carefully addressed in future applications of the mitigation hierarchy to offset biodiversity and ecosystem services loss. These critical points include:

- › The need to set up multi-scalar offsetting schemes that can consistently address biodiversity and ecosystem services issues at multiple levels (from the EU scale to the local scale).
- › The problem of finding suitable spaces to implement compensation actions, especially in marine areas, where ecosystems do not have fixed boundaries.
- › The inevitable uncertainty associated with how ecosystems actually evolve in offset sites (in terms of species composition, ecosystem structure and functioning, the evolution of the ecosystems over time due to external influences such as climate change, etc.).

4.2.3. Tools and practices that address the aspect of ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy

As the mitigation hierarchy is a framework, it has strong links with tools and practices that are used in making land- and resource-use decisions. Several panellists highlighted the **link between mitigation hierarchy and land-use planning** to incorporate ecosystem services and biodiversity knowledge into decision-making. *“Mitigation hierarchy avoiding or reducing the pressure must be going with a nice planning and really detailed planning, and MSP [Marine spatial planning] does it from the beginning stage”* [Panellist 7]. The EU has recognised the link between avoidance and MSP with the checklist toolbox, which proposes an ecosystem-based approach.

The link between mitigation hierarchy and land-use planning is especially important at the early stages of planning. Several panellists suggested that the avoid stage, particularly, is useful in emphasising where development should not occur. *“We have irreplaceable habitats, and they are truly irreplaceable, you can’t do net gain if you lose them, they’re just irreplaceable”* [Panellist 3]. However, panellists recognised that avoiding all impacts is impossible in practice, *“it’s always an intervention in an area that results in positive and negative impacts (...) So simply avoiding everything is impossible because you’ll be interfering in the environment.... Avoidance and mitigations are very intricately interwoven very often”* [Panellist 1]. It was stressed though, that “we have to

keep on talking also about avoiding as we can still do things there” [Panellist 4].

To avoid impacts, the panellists emphasised that it is key to know if there are any sensitive biodiversity spots, what ecosystem services are produced, what ecological condition the ecosystem under investigation is in, and what pressures biodiversity and ecosystem services face. In the avoidance stage, *“we can understand which areas potentially in the future will be under pressure, and specific recommendations or regulations can be defined for this kind of analysis”* [Panellist 7]. There was a general consensus in the panel that it is **important to work with spatial tools to identify conflict areas and pressures** to deal in planning to avoid future

Bilbao harbour windfarm.

photo © Andy Hay

negative impacts. For this, modelling can help: *“we were checking using the Bayesian Belief Networks, trying to identify the best areas, the most suitable areas and most sustainable areas for offshore wind platforms in Basque country but at the same time in the Eastern Atlantic Coast,”* [Panellist 7]. However, *“There will always be an impact [if we interfere in the environment], but it depends on the perception of the stakeholders and the experts involved, whether it’s acceptable or not - whether you have more positive consequences, or you have negative”* [Panellist 1].

Furthermore, it is important to consider **cumulative impacts and risk-based assessments**; panellist 9 explained that *there is the potential to incorporate risk-based assessment into cumulative impact assessments, “For example, to better frame the cumulative effect assessment but also the MSP [Marine Spatial Planning]; to try to harmonise the concept provided by the mitigation hierarchy with the risk-based assessment could offer a better opportunity to the methodology to be directly used from the practitioners and the planners, and so on - a good next step for that can be implemented.”*

It is worth noting that ecosystem and ecosystem services mapping can reveal that **impacts have already happened**, and the question then becomes **what is the baseline for mitigation hierarchy – to avoid or to restore?** Panellist 8 explained from their experience, *“After we had mapped this ecosystem condition and ecosystem services, we found out that it’s not too good the condition of our natural*

ecosystems, especially in the forests and the fields in agriculture. But it's good that we have these maps at the moment, and we can use it [for] decision-makers. Also, this is how it is at the moment, we should do something, we should preserve something that we already have, at least. Very important is that we have this spatial data”.

4.2.4. Current use of mitigation hierarchy in policies and regulations

Some countries have **incorporated mitigation hierarchy principles into their laws**, with some countries of Europe applying it “*more strategically in land use plans*” [Panellist 2]. Not all planning laws are helpful, though, for example, “*quite old regional rules and regional plans for land. Not so effective, not so good in avoiding the impact of the process*” [Panellist 5]. It has been reported that “*the mitigation hierarchy is not very consistently used*” [Panellist 4] in land-use laws except for coastal land use, where “*they want to avoid the most biodiverse rich areas. While in other laws, there is not usually the requirement to find the most unharmed spot for certain projects.*” [Panellist 4]. Also, it is **difficult to assess the mitigation hierarchy use in land use plans**, as decisions taken to apply the avoidance stage of the mitigation hierarchy are not clearly stated [Panellist 2]. Some municipal land use plans state they want to use the “no net loss approach”, an aspect of the mitigation hierarchy. There are examples of pilot projects applying the concept in practice [Panellist 4, e.g., Ekoteko project in Finland].

Building laws and the Environmental Impact Assessment are also relevant for applying the mitigation hierarchy. Some countries have introduced the concept of ecosystem services in their building laws, such as in Germany [Panellist 2]. However, the German tool seems more focused on offsetting, the last stage of the mitigation hierarchy, rather than avoidance. Panellists stressed that the avoidance stage in the Environmental Impact Assessment still plays a minor role due to unclear wording. In addition, project approvals are unbalanced since developers hold more power than other actors. Another problem highlighted is that: “*in environmental impact assessment, it says that you have to look for alternatives, but it does not always mean that you have to look for alternative locations*” [Panellist 4].

In some countries, there are specific regulations for how you **mitigate and compensate forest clearing (deforestation)**: “*the rationale for that is that those forests provide services, and so when you determine if and how you should give a permit for that clearing, then ecosystem service aspects (...) such as the leisure activity, green spaces, all of that is taken on board*” [Panellist 2]. Other regulations that might be linked are those related to **gas and oil extraction in the sea** [Panellist 9].

General **EU policies** mentioned by the panellists linked to the mitigation hierarchy avoidance stage include: the EU biodiversity strategy - i.e., the No-Net-Loss objective; the EU Green Deal; CAP; the EU Soil Strategy 2030; and the EU taxonomy.

Provisioning services or evidence of biodiversity loss?

photo © Simi Savilaakso

Furthermore, it has been suggested that **international bodies' funding project policy tools** are successful examples of implementation.

For example, “*the IFC [International Finance Corporation] criteria are still the strongest around the world, but I must say for example, that the EIB [European Investment Bank] has developed guidelines for hydropower which are revolutionary*” [Panellist 1]. Taxes are also potential policies to impact the avoidance stage: “*some municipality councils received (...) a proposal to increase the local taxes, local fees for new buildings in order to avoid the new land take and reuse of the already taken areas in the cities*” [Panellist 5].

To sum up, links to the policies that may be used to implement the mitigation hierarchy can be listed based on the following **multilevel approach**:

International level: Guidelines on Environmental Impact Assessment/Strategic Environmental Assessments,

EU level: policies on biodiversity,

National level: policies on zoning,

Local/municipal level: policies on zoning and taxation.

4.2.5 Use of ecosystem services concept and mitigation hierarchy

4.2.5.1. Challenges

Panellists highlighted various challenges with mitigation hierarchy definitions. “There’s so many different definitions of it and the ways to frame it - that doesn’t help. Because when you get inconsistency, it undermines the concept of it” [Panellist 3]. **Unclear definitions** often lead to unclear rules and a lack of consistent application of concepts, a concern of many panellists. “It’s too easy to jump this step, the mitigation and go directly to compensation... [and] In some cases municipalities that are not following these principles, guidelines at all” [Panellist 5].

Furthermore, the mitigation hierarchy framework faces multiple issues at varying levels of **governance and implementation**.

Global frameworks are being developed where discussions on biodiversity are “not even bothering to put a quantitative assessment on the avoidance side of things because it’s not clear how to do that” [Panellist 10]. As mentioned earlier, discussions at all levels can be hampered by **power imbalances**, and as Panellist 2 notes: “Mitigation and compensation are a tool to find a common ground. The problem with that is that the parties who are around the table to find this common ground are not equals” where those “working on endangered species hold much less power in that discussion than, you know, the multinational with deep pockets or that has managed to obtain strong support from government authorities etc.”.

It has also been argued that **policymakers are “not passionate” about biodiversity** and generally “not so open to new policies” [Panellist 6]. “My concern is how we will keep this concept and that this is not just the 10 years’ fashion” [Panellist 6]. However, Panellist 11 suggested that “politicians have been very welcoming to these new ideas” to incorporate ecological thinking. Panellist 6 also pointed out how **many governments are not stable**, so politicians are reluctant to take action as they are focused on short-term gains because, as Panellist 2 says, “defining a target is difficult”, and “not having a target is a good way for politicians to not take a stand and remain ambiguous and make everyone happy”.

Who gets a seat at the table and whose power counts when nature is in the balance?

Photo © Pop H

Weaknesses at the national level of policymaking can pose a threat to local-level implementation. **Weak local-level capacity** can threaten national biodiversity strategies and so on. As Panellist 2 argues, “it’s going to be a multilevel governance system that you’d have to put in place (...). That’s why some of the biodiversity issues, some of the ecosystem services issues are managed at the EU level and others are managed only locally (...) it’s not, national versus local”. This can be further amplified by a **lack of knowledge and education**: “We know how to do it because we have been trained on how to do it. But that’s not always the case, to be very honest, we have lots of things to learn” [Panellist 11]. They go on to argue that large multidisciplinary teams are needed. Panellist 2, however, highlighted that “local governments don’t necessarily have the capacity or the staff to guide them on the technical aspects. This is exacerbated by problems with “defining who have the main competences at the national level” [Panellist 5].

A lack of resources, effective design, monitoring and application in practice were challenges highlighted by several panellists because “in order to avoid the sensitive areas, you should know where the sensitive areas are, and lack of data is a really big important problem I see” [Panellist 7]. In other words, it is important “to have good data about where you can and cannot do a project” [Panellist 2].

“We need something to show that no, you can’t go there - you can’t waste all these remaining ecosystems in good condition, you have to choose between them, and then you may build into already disturbed areas.” [Panellist 8]. But “We really need a lot of resources to carry out investigations in marine areas. I see a lot still needs to be investigated” [Panellist 6]. And in the end, it **all comes down to money** and attitudes towards it “when talking about benefits... there might be still the economic valuation. I also know that there are different attitudes towards making a price tag or estimations in society and also among politicians” [Panellist 6], and in practice, “Money is a big issue to the cities that are now trying to apply it [mitigation hierarchy] to their land use planning. as always, it’s [the] economy, at least short-term economy, that rules” [Panellist 4]. The main threat is that developers “want to build where it’s the most cheap” [Panellist 8], “in practice compensation is never costly enough” [Panellist 2].

Also, having tools, even those mandated in regulations, does not mean they are effective in avoiding impacts or mitigating them. As Panellist 10 highlights, *“I have plenty of concerns about whether it’s done properly or not, whether it’s effectively resourced, whether it’s effectively designed (the kind of the offsets and avoidance measures), whether it’s defective, where whether it’s monitored, whether it’s actually done in practice, whether people are transparent about the plans and then the outcomes of the biodiversity offsets they build”*. In other words, the **link between mitigation hierarchy and the tool can be strong in theory but weak in practice**: *“Then the other examples I’ve run nowadays into very, very often because I’m now involved in a panel of experts for the European Commission for the international cooperation agenda, and we have to judge all the proposed projects, and we get a very, very short notice. We get a very short summary of any proposed project they want to fund, and then we usually have to ask for Environmental Impact Assessment, and then, in the end, they come up with an Environmental Impact Assessment - you see that it’s a tick mark exercise. Their project has to do an Environmental Impact Assessment, you get the obvious preferred alternative, and then usually they have a few other alternatives, which they made up and didn’t assess very seriously, (...)The quality still is simply unacceptable in terms of trying to avoid negative impacts, let alone try to do good for the environment [Panellist 1]”*. Thus, **assessment times are too short for meaningful evaluation** of the case. As Panellist 5 points out, authorities have a duty to carry out monitoring activities to control and guide the processes of development.

Finally, the **focus on the avoid stage was highlighted as a weakness** by two panellists arguing that a more pragmatic stance should be taken. Panellist 10 suggested that *“minimisation is also important”*. However, Panellist 1 argues *“that it [mitigation hierarchy] doesn’t include the very first phase”*, that we should *“build back better”*, and *“the first step should be enhanced”*.

Ecosystem service impacts or benefits? Does this avoid biodiversity loss by being sited on a heavily used beach area?

photo © 8Forest

4.2.5.2. Opportunities

Several strengths and opportunities where the mitigation hierarchy could be used at different levels and in varying situations were suggested. Three panellists agreed that the mitigation hierarchy is getting **increased attention and application** at local/municipality and regional levels. In contrast, Panellist 10 identified the opportunity to use the mitigation hierarchy at a national level as a *“kind of extension (...) towards the idea of a conservation hierarchy, where you’re looking at national scale application in the mitigation hierarchy”*. One panellist identified the use of the mitigation hierarchy within a No-Net-Loss approach, and another suggested that financial institutions also have an important role to play by not funding *“this project because this is a really critical habitat”* [Panellist 2].

Two panellists identified the **use of payment mechanisms** in the context of the mitigation hierarchy. This includes, for instance, local scale application by municipalities for land use planning payments for ecosystem services modification. This proposal would include increasing *“the local taxes local fees for new buildings, in order to avoid the new land take and reuse the already taken areas in the cities”* [Panellist 5]. Panellist 10 identified a mechanism for compensation from multinational corporations to *“evaluate their biodiversity impacts year on year and then use the mitigation hierarchy as*

a framework for how they minimise, mitigate and ultimately compensate for those [impacts on] the biodiversity of their activities.

Panellist 3 sees the opportunity for the mitigation hierarchy to be used... *within a risk assessment framework – “this could better join this methodology with the MSP [Marine Spatial Planning] or other processes, it can provide a common background”*. **Risk-based analysis** can be particularly useful in territorial and Marine Spatial Planning processes and within Blue Growth strategies.

4.2.6. Future directions

A diversity of views emerged from the panellists concerning future directions, in particular concerning pressures. Three panellists explicitly stated that the ecosystem services concept may be a good instrument to deal with environmental challenging topics; Panellist 6 further suggested

that it was “important to keep the topic of ecosystem services alive”. In the same vein, two panellists mention the Green Deal and one Blue Growth that provide a framework to support different perceptions that may influence national policy sectors. These concepts were highlighted for their potential to support the first stage of the mitigation hierarchy, avoidance. However, they are not without opposition, as exemplified by panellist 2: “Currently, we are in favour (as environmentalists), we have a Green Deal policy, [and] biodiversity targets (are very strict now) on how to establish protected areas - land and marine areas. But ... we also are creating very strong opposition from people who want to generate income or money, because they get restrictions or limitations, where to go and what to do.

Panellist 1 suggested that **participation and early intervention** meant better outcomes, “and that’s the ideal situation that you try to avoid potential unacceptable negative impacts.” Panellist 8 suggested that people were developing **an awareness concerning the environment, and greater value was being put on nature**. For example, “a very strong confrontation from ordinary people” helped to ensure detrimental laws were not passed in one case. Production of ecosystem service maps of the country was also an asset for raising knowledge on the value of nature to people.

There is a perception that there is more information on terrestrial systems, “where you have been studying a lot, so you know what impact will cost” [Panellist 6] to deal with pressures and impacts. **This contrasts with marine systems** where there is “bigger uncertainty. It’s also much more difficult to justify why we need to avoid - might be we don’t need it!” [Panellist 6] In general, the lack of deep knowledge of different systems, pressures and impacts seems to be of critical importance to be able to plan for the future and deploy different mechanisms such as compensation to deal with trade-offs and decision-making to be able to plan for future directions. This is particularly important, as pointed out by Panellist 6, “when (...) politicians are also asking concrete arguments or facts, and you are proposing to avoid some activities”.

Another important consideration is the **spatial dimension to be able to know where to avoid or compensate** “is an opportunity to protect the nature because if we have the maps and materials

where we can show the most valuable ecosystems in good condition, then we can say where it should be preserved” [Panellist 8], followed by “In planning protected areas, (...). We need to prove more that these protected areas are necessary so that we need to preserve these communities and ecosystems in these specific areas (...) there are places where we have to avoid - in protected areas, the offsetting part is not even applicable at all”; Other than the spatial dimension it is also important **the temporal dimension towards the future** to be considered in planning projects concerning protected areas “You have to think more about the long term impacts on biodiversity, even though you don’t go through a protected area, so that’s a bit to mitigation hierarchy” [Panellist 1].

Greater uncertainty exists in marine ecosystems on what to avoid.

photo © Sandra Luque

4.3 Further insights from the Applied Policy Delphi panel and case studies found in the literature

After the first round of the Applied Policy Delphi process was completed and the results of the systematic mapping were shared with the panellists, further research was undertaken by the EWG on the points raised during the Applied Policy Delphi process. In this section, we present the results from the second round of the Applied Policy Delphi process combined with insights from the case studies found in the literature. We have included the questions

that were posed to the Applied Policy Delphi panel members under each heading for clarity.

4.3.1. Enhance stage in the mitigation hierarchy

Q1. Should the mitigation hierarchy embrace the enhance stage, or will this complicate the concept unnecessarily? By enhance, we mean, for example, adding green spaces to developments.

Seven panellists were divided on whether an “enhance” stage should be included in the mitigation hierarchy. Three panellists felt it would complicate or muddle the hierarchy [Panellists 1, 2 & 8], especially since it is a recognised and well-established framework [Panellist 10]. Panellists 2 and 4 suggested that this would lead to a risk of developments with low-grade green spaces overriding the correct application of mitigation hierarchy principles; for example, green areas added to housing developments. Panellist 8 pointed out that the application of an enhance

stage implies that “we assume that some impact has already happened/is going to be happen and then it would not be avoidance or first stage of the hierarchy anymore”. This, therefore, implies that enhance is essentially about the restoration of degraded environments. Panellist 4 added, “enhancing implies that we can ‘create better’ than what existing nature already is. The term should rather be part of the mitigation hierarchy, but the government should make regulations that require avoiding and minimising first. Otherwise, it will be grass and tulips”. Panellists 1, 3 and 5, however, felt this stage would improve the mitigation hierarchy application as “it should specify the outcome for biodiversity to achieve by following the mitigation hierarchy, i.e., net gains” [Panellist 3].

Panellist 6 suggested that if the enhance stage was added, then the mitigation hierarchy name should be changed to mitigation governance, as this would broaden the scope of the mitigation hierarchy to embrace the enhance stage.

There is no explicit evidence found in the literature reviewed in this study for the use of the enhance stage within the mitigation hierarchy. However, in our opinion, the enhance concept could be applied as an overarching theme to support biodiversity conservation and the health and well-being of society rather than in the hierarchy itself. Examples of how this could be applied is in the use of brownfield sites rather than new sites so that green belt land is protected from urban sprawl (Cullen, 2006) or in the provision of corridors to connect high-quality habitats (Tarabon, 2019a). Kowarik (2021) makes the distinction between “ancient wilderness”, or remnants of nature in need of conservation or restoration and “novel wilderness” arising from degraded urban-post-industrial sites. These novel wilderness areas reflect the enhance concept, where designers have incorporated them into green infrastructure, thus supporting biodiversity and providing additional ecosystem services to society.

Schulp et al. (2016) argue that spatial flexibility potentially brings higher gains for biodiversity and ecosystem services, as does the provision of corridors to connect high-quality habitats in Tarabon (2019a). Therefore, we suggest embracing the concept of enhancement as an umbrella term

to frame a biodiverse future that brings multiple benefits to society, i.e., is net positive for nature and people. It can help to set a more positive tone in the land-use debate that recognises the important role that biodiversity plays. In conclusion, the term enhance is not a useful term within the mitigation hierarchy itself but may prove useful in framing a more positive debate around land use for the benefit of biodiversity and society.

4.3.2. Inclusion of ecosystem services and risk to biodiversity

Q2. Does including ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy pose a risk for bio-diversity conservation because provisioning ecosystem services might take preference over biodiversity?

photo © Sini Savilaakso

If ecosystem services are included, how do we ensure biodiversity conservation?

Out of the seven panellists who answered the question, three panellists [2, 3 and 8] expressed concern with including ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy due to the potential risks it poses in biodiversity conservation. This is because provisioning ecosystem services are “easy to assess” [Panellist 8] and because “biodiversity might be downplayed against much more vocal and organised interest groups that will favour intensive agriculture, forestry, fisheries (a.k.a. provisioning ecosystem services)” [Panellist 2]. However, Panellist 2 does suggest

London is a city surrounded by a green belt which includes high biodiversity areas but is under huge pressure for development and green belt release.

that there are opportunities to connect biodiversity to social challenges though “in the context of an Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA)... as long as the biodiversity issues remain under their own standard (e.g., “net gain”)”.

In contrast, panellists 4, 5, 6 and 10 see the potential to incorporate ecosystem services into the mitigation hierarchy, for example, by including “conservation” as an ecosystem service, where conservation may consist of a mix of regulations applied to more than one ecosystem service [Panellist 1]. However, Panellist 5 suggests that biodiversity and ecosystem services should be kept separated in the evaluation in order to better protect irreplaceable areas.

In addition, Panellist 10 suggested defining an “accounting for the social impacts of No Net Loss type policies”. This would allow the social dimension

values and non-values associated with biodiversity loss to be accounted for in projects. The panellist also suggests introducing the concept of no-worse-off (Griffiths et al., 2017). No-worse-off does not substitute the No-Net-Loss of biodiversity but works in parallel to ensure social equity of the process and people's well-being and health. Panellist 8 added that it was necessary to assess and map regulating and cultural ecosystem services to create a "stronger case" for the implications of biodiversity loss and conservation. Panellist 4 suggested it would be good to integrate ecosystem services into the mitigation hierarchy, but it should not be made too complicated since mitigation hierarchy, especially the aspects of ecological compensations, are complicated enough alone. Also, they argue that there should be a hierarchy of ecosystem services; for example, life-serving ecosystem services should be prioritised and safeguarded before those ecosystem services that grant economic profits.

The literature showed that although there is increasing support for the use of ecosystem services in planning, there is little evidence in the mitigation hierarchy literature that the use of ecosystem services poses a threat to biodiversity. A wider search of the literature is needed to bring these elements together as the expert working group is aware of the literature that suggests the use of ecosystem services does potentially impact biodiversity. In the marine environment, according to (Azzellino et al., 2013; Farella et al., 2021), there is no evidence of ecosystem services being used in marine assessment and mapping procedures. However, Farella et al. (2021) use regulatory measures and zoning principles to mitigate impacts on marine biodiversity (habitats, seabirds, mammals, fish) from human activities. According to Kyriazi et al. (2016), the governance of marine natural resources means trade-offs between multiple biotic ecosystem services conserved through a Marine Protected Area (MPA) and the enabling of abiotic ecosystem services (wind, wave of tidal energy) in its spatial proximity as a societal demand for energy. However, the preference for biodiversity conservation over abiotic energy provision and vice versa does not always occur as they may co-exist in marine realms. In terrestrial environments, Eyvindson et al. (2018) demonstrate that combining different forest management regimes reduces the negative effects

of increasing harvest levels to biodiversity and non-wood ecosystem services. Good landscape-level forest management planning is crucial to minimise ecological costs by prioritising biodiversity values that need to be safeguarded. Biodiversity and ecosystem processes, however, are not evenly distributed over time and space, and that may result in a mismatch of priorities between biodiversity and ecosystem services. Using a landscape-level assessment (Hayes et al., 2015) demonstrates that key biodiversity and ecological processes that characterise a landscape can also support a wide range of ecosystem services in an equitable manner. Lerouge et al. (2017) state that buffer zones provide spatial resilience to biological functions and services to protect against internal and external shocks.

Life-serving.

Photo © Joanna Storie

Spatial resilience, however, is a socio-ecological system term. Schulp et al. (2016) identifies the effectiveness of policy options in a mitigation hierarchy context by distinguishing biodiversity and ecosystem services. However, it remains challenging to achieve No Net Loss for biodiversity and ecosystem services at a large spatial scale.

The Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystem Services (MAES) process in Europe proved to be a very constructive and successful way to engage stakeholders from the member states, test methods and deliver relevant outcomes. Some successful examples from Bulgaria (Nedkov et al., 2018), Latvia (Ruskule et al., 2018), among others (Santos-Martin et al., 2018), provided good insights in terms of the advantage of mapping ecosystem services to improve assessments. However, it was difficult to downscale the process from the national level to the territorial planning level in order to reach practical outputs to target the needs of avoiding or/mitigating biodiversity loss. Still, the integration of ecosystem services supported knowledge development and cooperation to improve biodiversity conservation (Maes et al., 2012, 2018).

4.3.3. Implementing effective avoidance

Q3: What does effective avoidance look like, at what level should it happen, e.g., landscape, species, ecosystems, and how do you measure it?

All panellists who responded to the question agreed that "avoidance should happen at all scales, from policies, (programmes), plans to projects"

[Panellist 2] and from species to ecosystems. “*The level depends on the intended scale of activities*” [Panellist 6], and determining the “*appropriate level should be project-specific*” [Panellist 5]. Moving from species to landscape and ecosystem level makes avoidance more complicated as ecological corridors and other essential elements of ecological networks are often not under protection. Hence, early stages of development were emphasised, as this is when decisions to use or not to use untouched sites can be taken. Four panellists highlighted the importance that “*development is planned based on spatial / mapped conservation priorities with zones of development and zones of no-development based on conservation priorities*” [Panellist 3]. This makes avoidance effective and “*makes business sense as it is a much more cost-effective way to plan [compared to the current system]*” [Panellist 3]. Of course, “*to choose, which areas have to be untouched, a good input spatial data of the ecosystems, their ecological connectivity and other aspects characterising their condition and ecological value is needed*” as Panellist 8 put it.

Only three panellists commented on how effective avoidance should be measured, but those that did highlight the need to measure both actions (what actions are taken) and outcomes (what happens on the ground, i.e., impacts of actions) [Panellist 3, X] and the cost aspects “*It should be measurable in the same units as offsets to allow a loss gain balance*” [Panellist 10].

The evidence from case studies and policy documents is aligned with the panellists’ views. Case studies support early analysis of potential direct and cumulative impacts as a means for effective avoidance (Bigard et al., 2017, 2020), as well as avoidance measures targeting all levels from landscape to species that take into account connectivity (Bigard et al., 2020; Pontoppidan MB & Nachman G, 2013; Sahraoui et al., 2021; Tarabonet et al., 2019b). The importance of landscape scale is emphasised, especially in places undergoing rapid landscape changes (Tarabonet et al., 2019a). Based on their analysis of several Environmental Impact Assessments over a decade, Bigard et al. (2017) conclude that: “*The development of a territorial strategy that shifts from an approach based on treating “symptoms” at the scale of individual projects to a more preventive approach focused on the avoidance of*

biodiversity loss and mitigation of cumulative impacts is now necessary”. Similarly to the panellists’ views, mapping and good input spatial data are highlighted in several of the case studies (e.g., Bennett, 2018; Pontoppidan & Nachman, 2013; Tarabonet et al., 2019a; Tarabonet et al., 2019b.) and incorporating biodiversity into natural capital assessments is recommended (Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020).

4.3.4. Improving the effectiveness of the decision-making process

Q4. Stakeholders have different degrees of power to influence decisions under the mitigation hierarchy. How can the decision-making process that supports the delivery of mitigation hierarchy be made more effective?

Citizens should be involved as early as possible and kept involved during the land use planning process.

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Of the six panellists who answered this question, each interpreted it in a different way. They all agreed that the mitigation hierarchy should be incorporated into the initial stages of decision-making, policy design and planning. Panellist 2 also suggests that consideration of ecosystem services is one way of incorporating stakeholders into the process. Panellist 3 argues that the most effective application of the mitigation hierarchy is “*at the earliest possible stage*” of policymaking, for example, locally when development plans are made. Panellist 4 stated that research in Finland

concluded that citizens should be involved as early as possible and kept involved during the land use planning process (or the Environmental Impact Assessment process). However, the process of applying the mitigation hierarchy should be made more clearly a part of these processes. As panellist 4 explains, it is especially difficult in land use planning to get all segments of society to participate in public hearings etc.

While the answers provided by the six panellists were not explicit regarding the effectiveness of citizens’ engagement in mitigation hierarchy decision-making processes, they all agreed that support mechanisms were important, such as legislation and regulation. Panellists 2 and 6 highlighted the challenges of implementation and enforcement of the European legislative framework. This is due to the discrepancies in incorporating EU law and policy into national regulations and in the capacity and political

will of those involved in enforcing it [Panellist 2 & 6]. Panellist 10 highlights that it is a challenging problem, as the proper application of the mitigation hierarchy requires consideration of avoidance measures very early on in the project concept design and planning stages. Whilst they would advocate for including community stakeholders at that stage, they highlight that the input needs to be treated meaningfully, and such input could substantially alter the direction of the entire project; they are, therefore, “sceptical about the degree to which project proponents would accept that! So, this is a tricky one”.

With regard to the dynamic of the decision-making process, Panellist 10 argues that there is a difference between equity, which refers to a power imbalance in the decision-making process, where stakeholders have different levels of recognition, reputation and influence, and efficacy, where the power dynamics results in good decision-making. Panellist 8 suggested a practical measure to encourage social participation was to raise the awareness of “*the value of other valuable ecosystems and their processes*” and to integrate them “*into spatial plans and in the decision-making process as a whole*”. Panellist 5 added that an “*explicit definition of impacts*” will help to increase public awareness. Panellist 11 added from their experience that in “*any participatory process, there is a need to explain and educate people on the qualities of the ecosystem services. If properly done, the communities will not just support an ecosystem service approach; they will embrace it*”. Panellist 1 also suggests that people can easily understand the role nature plays in providing water to drink, air to breathe, food to eat and a place to live safely. So, in this respect, it is not a difficult topic to comprehend at this level.

The scientific evidence underlines the need to consider the environment in strategic decision-making across various sectors and activities, as the panellists suggested. The need for the engagement of stakeholders is one of the governance aspects mentioned in the literature. Several studies reported the engagement of stakeholders, namely (Fontaine et al., 2014; Ottersen et al., 2011; Sahraoui et al., 2021; Schulp et al., 2016). The engagement of stakeholders, who were experts in the field, included ranking co-existence challenges and opportunities (Farella et al., 2021; Kyriazi et al., 2016). In addition,

the conservation NGOs are engaged in working with companies to develop conservation strategies (CEMEX UK & RSPB, 2020), and the stakeholder consultation and involvement throughout the entire design process is reported in Iberdrola (2019). In Sahraoui (2021), co-creation brings various actors together, but it was perceived that there was a lack of participation by the public authorities. The community-based research is mentioned explicitly in only two articles that refer to meetings with local fishermen (Aunins et al., 2018) and local forest managers’ participation (Fontaine et al., 2014).

The literature showed that most studies dedicated to the mitigation hierarchy do not include community-based stakeholders. The usual suspects continue

Photo © Sandra Luque

Ecosystems may reflect different values depending on the user's perspective.

to be the target audience, and when they participate, their engagement occurs during the co-design or co-implementation phases, in some instances as consultants. This lack of diversity of stakeholders makes us question whether there is a lack of recognition of non-technical and non-academic knowledge or the influence of socio-political dimensions within the mitigation hierarchy agenda. In addition, it is unclear whether the opportunities for participation include stakeholders at all stages of the decision-making process and at which level of intensity (consultation, information, collaboration, co-production, empowerment).

Significant values agreed on by stakeholders’ active involvement are highlighted in Fontaine et al. (2014) as a way to improve the appreciation of ecosystem services concept by citizens to decision-makers and to identify the owners and beneficiaries of ecological functions. For instance, the VOTE (Fontaine et al., 2014) as a framework solution focused on ecosystem services participatory valuation to achieve sustainable ecosystem services management. Despite some authors highlighting the risks of ignoring customers’ or citizens’ values (Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020; Cullen, 2006), there is no active involvement of stakeholders mentioned in their literature.

Generally speaking, there is consensus in the literature regarding the importance of citizen engagement, but, hitherto, the roles, the tools, the responsiveness, and the degrees are still unspecified. The lack of literature that scrutinises what really

happens in the application of the mitigation hierarchy decision-making process is an obstacle to understanding the power imbalance and dynamics, as mentioned by the Applied Policy Delphi panel.

4.3.5. Strengthening capacity to implement mitigation hierarchy

Q5. Education and capacity are clearly weaknesses at various levels/settings. In your opinion, at which level/setting is the need to strengthen the capacity the greatest? How would this influence the discourse on trade-offs?

Out of the five panellists who answered this question, four stressed the influence of power on education and capacity as a weakness, and two stressed the need for better education to improve the capacity to make better decisions.

Panellist 6 suggested that the lack of capacity is related to “power imbalances among stakeholders”. Panellist 2 argues that “The current pressure to expedite environmental permitting (e.g., for renewable energy) is likely to make power imbalances worse” and suggests strategy games as an approach to improve environmental decision-making. They also emphasised it is “important to give the less powerful time to organise, fund-raise, etc.” and that transparency is crucial. However, Panellist 6 stated that “even if the process is transparent with public participation, still the politicians will take decisions according to their political priorities, considering trade-offs. Mitigation hierarchy can only support wiser, smarter decisions, but still, the decisions cannot be in favour of biodiversity conservation but for socio-economic benefits”.

Regarding the need for building capacity, panellist 8 suggested that “raising awareness, giving solid facts and scenarios (“what happens if”) and explanations of the benefits that protection of nature entails might help”. For this, we need “better background information (consistent data collection about nature, not only species but the overall state of the ecosystems, etc.), better tools for communication, visualisation, etc.” Indeed, to educate, knowledge is needed, followed by effective communication.

Panellist 10 suggested that “the greatest need for capacity [building] surely has to be in validation,

enforcement, and monitoring – at the scale of local/regional public decision-makers”. They also suggested that those enforcing policies should be able to “enforce penalties for non-compliance”. Panellist 3, however, pointed out that even if capacity building and education is needed at all levels, “the senior leadership who have the biggest influence on decision-making, be this in Government and industry, and the financial sector,” must be considered as a priority.

Within the literature that applies the mitigation hierarchy in case studies, there is little information on the limiting factors of education and capacity. This may reflect the use of experts in the field as stakeholders, as detailed in the previous section.

Hayes et al. (2015), however, highlight the “lack of the capacity and resources for enforcement in many developing nations”. They also say that there is a “lack of capacity within both governments and companies themselves and a lack of data with which to assess impacts”. Also, “insufficient funding for education and awareness raising” is also highlighted (Aunins et al., 2018).

The lack of knowledge and sufficient expertise in relevant government departments and agencies has been confirmed by Moreira (2019). Whilst the issue of weak enforcement and poor long-term monitoring is supported by evidence in national

case studies, the lack of knowledge is a barrier to effective enforcement and monitoring (Moreira, 2019). This has been seen, for example, when valuing the impact of energy projects in the marine environment (Kyriazi et al., 2016).

4.3.6. Regulatory approaches towards avoidance

Q6. Is there a need for a stronger regulatory approach towards avoidance of impacts and inclusion of mitigation hierarchy in general? I.e., How can EU/national/regional laws improve the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy, or what alternatives are there to the regulatory approach?

Among the various tools that can support a shift towards the avoidance stage of the mitigation hierarchy or its valorisation, regulation has been mentioned by most of the seven panellists who answered this question (five panellists). Three

Whose values count, and how do we ensure that future generations are heard?

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panellists [Panellists 10, 5 and 3] support a stronger regulatory approach, and three [Panellists 10, 8 and 6] point out possible reasons why regulations fail to achieve their goals, such as how the mitigation hierarchy is only vaguely embedded in land-use planning. However, panellist 2 suggests that it does depend on the country and the regulatory framework already in place. Among those suggesting a stronger regulatory approach, Panellist 10 reports that there is evidence that stronger regulation ensures more widespread and effective implementation of the mitigation hierarchy. Likewise, Panellist 3, drawing on the UK as an example, supports a stronger regulatory approach to strengthen avoidance in land planning in high biodiversity areas where the development is extremely time-consuming and costly. Panellist 5 suggests a “national-level adoption of the hierarchy as the ‘normal principle’ of planning” with an explicit monitoring strategy.

Notwithstanding the advantages of regulations, the experts recognised the following obstacles that are likely to hinder the regulatory approach:

- 1. Lack of a clear **definition** and framing of avoidance in regulations [Panellist 10];
- 2. **Weak enforcement and monitoring** of the outcomes of the avoidance stage, e.g., a public register on the model of offsetting public registers [Panellist 10];
- 3. Insufficient **technical capacity** of regulators, especially of local government officials and those not working in the environmental sector but still involved in development projects, e.g., finance officials [Panellist 8]. Panellist 6 adds that education and capacity are needed at all levels since “staff are frequently changing”.

The evidence primarily supports the current role of regulations when it comes to mitigation hierarchy. Indeed, most countries require impact avoidance to be considered as part of the Environmental and Social Impact Assessment process (Pope et al., 2013). However, other studies point out various hindering factors, which include those mentioned by the panellists but are not limited to them. The **lack of a clear definition** is supported by various case studies. Bigard et al. (2017) provided evidence from the introduction of a new policy in France in 2010 to integrate the Environmental

Impact Assessment legislation (law n 2010-788). Likewise, the definition of “environmental objective” in England’s National Planning Policy Framework (Cullen, 2006) is too vague. To overcome this, these scholars propose that consulting agencies provide clearer explanations or standardised methods. Likewise, the case study by Bigard et al. (2017) shows that avoidance should take place in the early stage of project development. For Gelot and Bigard (2021), a clear definition of the stakeholders’ roles and responsibilities is also needed to enter the correct information into datasets and allow effective long-term monitoring of the mitigation hierarchy at the national scale (see below).

Generally, **weak enforcement and insufficient technical expertise** hamper the

application of the hierarchy. However, a joint report by CEMEX UK & RSPB (2020) on the biodiversity management of quarry sites and the impact of extractive manufacturing industries in the UK highlights that good results can be achieved through the collaboration of local conservation officials and businesses. Gelot and Bigard (2021) show that the mitigation hierarchy in France has been poorly implemented and primarily focused on reduction/offset measures based on technical solutions rather than geographical or temporal solutions. They recommend nationwide, up-to-date datasets to improve enforcement

to support effective enforcement and monitoring (Moreira, 2019), especially in the marine environment (Kyriazi et al., 2016). In addition to the above, the evidence supports other issues equally likely to hinder the achievement of avoidance in regulations, e.g., the lack of **landscape-scale planning** (Bigard et al., 2020; Tarabon et al., 2019).

Lastly, the evidence shows the role of voluntary tools (third-party certification standards and financial loan requirements) are equally needed to create incentives and requirements for impact avoidance. Sustainability standards include those set by financial institutions, such as the Performance Standard of the International Finance Corporation, as well as **sector-specific standards**, such as those of the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil. Increasingly, however, companies are adopting commitments to No Net Loss or Net Positive Impact to reduce negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services

Photo © CHL

Landscape-scale planning is one of the key elements of the successful use of mitigation hierarchy.

(Gardner et al., 2013; Rainey et al., 2015). Biodiversity impact indicators and target setting for the analysis of **supply chains** have the potential of avoiding biodiversity impacts during business operations by first anticipating the potential impacts of business activity and then putting in place measures to prevent these adverse impacts (Cambridge Conservation Initiative, 2020). According to a recent report (BBOP, 2018), over 60 companies have now set ambitious biodiversity commitments towards No Net Loss or Net Positive Impact that will require significant avoidance of biodiversity impacts (see also Rainey et al., 2015). However, greater uptake of these internal policies will be needed for the widespread application of impact avoidance. A number of challenges remain with regard to effective avoidance. For example, the speed by which corporate decisions need to be made may preclude effective analysis of the avoidance options/need to avoid (Hayes et al., 2015).

4.3.7. Cost of compensation to incentivise impact avoidance

Q7. One panellist suggested that “in practice, compensation is never costly enough”. Do you have any thoughts or comments on this quote?

Five panellists who replied to the question agreed with the fact that compensation needs to be costly in order to properly account for everything that is lost (from carbon sequestration to people’s wellbeing), as well as to incentivise impact avoidance. However, the implementation of effective compensation measures requires transparency (i.e., the costs should be clearly disclosed) and a guarantee of enforcement by permitting authorities.

photo © Sandra Luque

Replaceable habitat?

Discussion

5. Discussion

5.1. Quality of evidence and knowledge gaps

During the research, we identified several knowledge gaps. There is a lack of studies on marine and freshwater environments. Terrestrial environments are more widely studied, but there were only a few studies on riparian landscapes and wetlands/peatlands. Geographically, studies from Eastern Europe are lacking.

Although the concept of mitigation hierarchy is relatively well known in the literature, when we look at avoid and mitigation stages of the mitigation hierarchy, the body of literature where the application of mitigation hierarchy in practice has been studied is small. This is especially true when we look at different topics linked with the application of the mitigation hierarchy. There is a lack of studies on risks, trade-offs and impacts. Also, the role of ecosystem services under the mitigation hierarchy has rarely been studied. We found hardly any literature that scrutinises what happens in the application of the mitigation hierarchy decision-making process in practice and the role and contributions of community-based stakeholders in that process.

Similarly, there was little information on the limiting factors of education and capacity. Overall, ecological aspects of avoid and mitigation stages have been studied more than social or governance aspects. However, to succeed in using mitigation hierarchy to its full potential in practice, we need an understanding of all three aspects.

We used the Applied Policy Delphi to supplement the literature and address knowledge gaps. Hence, the results and recommendations presented in this report are based on the best available evidence. Of course, there is an element of subjectiveness in the Applied Policy Delphi process, and the panel composition may have influenced the results. However, the results from the Applied Policy Delphi aligned with the literature and within the panel, indicating agreement on the topics. Where panel members had differing views, we have noted those in the text to give an unbiased perspective.

5.2. Enhancing landscapes through the use of mitigation hierarchy

Based on our results, it is clear that there is room for improvement in understanding and implementing the concept of mitigation hierarchy in practice. There is a need to ensure the strengthening of the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy, especially the avoid stage, at the landscape level to protect remaining natural ecosystems as they are irreplaceable habitats. There is also a need to enhance managed landscapes to achieve overall net biodiversity gains. Therefore, we suggest embracing the positive concept of landscape-level enhancement (i.e., improving landscapes for biodiversity and ecosystem services) as an umbrella term to frame a biodiverse future that brings multiple benefits to society. We do not mean enhancement of natural areas in the sense of restoration but rather assessing our landscapes and thinking proactively about where to avoid, minimise or restore and how to ensure nature-positive developments to achieve landscapes that ensure net gains for biodiversity and human wellbeing. This also includes management practices required to ensure the biodiversity of the particularly biodiverse vulnerable landscapes, for example, management required of semi-natural grasslands and the wildlife management of expansive/invasive species (e.g., Růsiņa et al. 2017). Support for these managed landscapes is needed but outside of the scope of this report. The landscape-level enhancement framing can also help to set a more positive tone in the land-use debate that recognises the important role that biodiversity plays.

In the rest of the section, we will focus on how the conservation of biodiversity can be improved through the better application of mitigation hierarchy. A recent conceptual framework on avoidance by Bull et al. (2022), suggested by two panellists, highlights four different categories for environmental avoidance (drivers, what and how to avoid, and actors involved) and serves as a starting point for our discussion (Figure 12). To achieve effective avoidance at the country level, these categories need to be considered holistically rather than targeted separately on a case-by-case basis. We first address institutional and social drivers for avoiding impacts, then discuss effective avoidance, i.e., what to avoid and how, and finally address the need to build the actors' capacity in the implementation mitigation hierarchy. We will also discuss how to integrate ecosystem services into the mitigation hierarchy

02 WHAT TO AVOID

HIGHLIGHTS:

A need for a proactive approach to ensure effective avoidance:

- landscape-scale mapping of biodiversity and sensitive ecosystems along with their relevant ecosystem services
- A multi-species approach is important at the landscape scale

HIGHLIGHTS:

- Institutional drivers comprise policies and regulations and are key to ensure effective avoidance of impacts
- Social drivers of avoidance: Integrating different perspectives through stakeholder engagement
- Social drivers of avoidance: Mainstreaming ecosystem services as part of the mitigation hierarchy

categories for environmental avoidance

01 DRIVERS

HOW TO AVOID

03

HIGHLIGHTS:

- implement meaningful territorial strategies and build local capacity to understand and implement the strategies in an inclusive process
- Effective avoidance addresses cumulative impacts and considers spatio-temporal dimensions

HIGHLIGHTS:

- The scientific evidence underlines the complexity and dynamic nature of the issues involved and the necessity to clarify definitions and terminology to ensure common understanding
- Transparency and active participation are encouraged

ACTORS INVOLVED

04

Figure 12. A conceptual framework of different categories of environmental avoidance and key issues linked with them; adapted from Bull et al., 2022.

to make the social benefits of avoidance more visible and strengthen biodiversity conservation through synergies with ecosystem services. We will recommend actions that strengthen the implementation of the mitigation hierarchy in relation to the issues discussed.

5.3 Addressing drivers for avoiding impacts

5.3.1. Regulations and policies key to strengthening enforcement of the mitigation hierarchy

Institutional drivers comprise policies and regulations and are key to ensuring effective avoidance of impacts. Our results support a stronger regulatory approach to mitigation hierarchy from the EU to national levels. Although mitigation hierarchy exists in various regulations and guidance documents, it is not consistently and systematically applied across European countries and within different planning levels. As land-use planning is often a separate process from planning and conserving natural areas, effective application of mitigation hierarchy would require that it is systematically considered at all planning levels, from local to national, as an overarching principle of planning. The evidence indicates that existing systems do not guarantee effective implementation of the existing approaches, e.g., Environmental Impact Assessments, and hence, strengthening both regulations and their governance is recommended. Voluntary standards can support and provide guidance on impact avoidance but cannot be relied upon alone. There was consensus that a stronger focus

Box 1. France – leading the way in including mitigation hierarchy into legislation.

The first reference to the definition of the mitigation hierarchy in France dates back to 1976 with the approval of the law on nature protection (Loi relative à la protection de la nature n°76-629 du 10 Juillet 1976 and article L122-3 du code de l'environnement). This law stated that this procedure was to be followed when assessing projects, plans and programmes. In 2004, the adoption of the Charte de l'environnement with constitutional relevance marked a crucial step forward towards the recognition of a new human right related to the environment (art. 1, Droit de vivre dans un environnement équilibré et respectueux de la santé), as well as towards the obligation of public authorities to implement the precautionary principle (art.5, principe de précaution) to reduce the risk of environmental damages. In 2012, the development of a national doctrine on the mitigation hierarchy (Doctrine nationale relative à la séquence ERc «Eviter, Réduire, Compenser») led to the adoption of Guidelines on the mitigation hierarchy in 2013, aimed at harmonizing definitions of basic concepts. Finally, in 2016 the law on recovering biodiversity, nature and landscape (Loi de reconquête de la biodiversité, de la nature et des paysages n° 2016-1087 du 8 août 2016) added two crucial result obligations to the National Doctrine of 2012:1. First, the respect of the sequence order (and not just the mitigation hierarchy), and second, the non-realisation of the project if the impacts on biodiversity cannot be avoided, reduced, and compensated in a satisfactory and appropriate manner.

The 2016 Biodiversity Law also improved the definition of the principle of preventive action with regard to the mitigation hierarchy by adding a reference to the No-Net-Loss principle. The mitigation hierarchy must now be considered in each plan, programme or project affecting natural ecosystems and is controlled by the French environmental authorities for validation. The law also introduces the need to consider ecosystem services provided by nature (article L110-1). Although some tests have been developed to consider ecosystem services in impact assessments, there is no standard approach and clarification is needed on which approach exist and can be used. This is why the French Biodiversity Office requested Eklipse to find out how ecosystem services can be considered in plans, projects, programmes, policies, and associated impact assessments, with a particular focus on the avoid stage of the mitigation hierarchy.

should be put on avoidance and minimisation rather than offsetting. Based on our results and feedback from the panellists, we have made recommendations on a regulatory approach to ensure mitigation hierarchy is firmly established in law in all EU countries following the example of France (Box 1).

5.3.2. Social drivers of avoidance: Integrating different perspectives through stakeholder engagement

Social drivers of avoidance stem from different values and perspectives people have for nature and their local environment. It is clear from the results that there is a need to be more inclusive of different perspectives, and the active involvement of different stakeholders needs to be strengthened. The literature showed that in nearly all case studies dedicated to the mitigation hierarchy, community-based stakeholders were not included, apart from cases reported, which included the engagement of local fishermen (Farella et al., 2021; ICES 2016). Thus, it is crucial to challenge the viewpoints of scientific and non-scientific players when assessing the sustainability of local ecosystems through the services they can provide to the local community. Although it is documented that a sustainable development scenario is developed with the contribution of stakeholders (Sahraoui et al., 2016), a number of studies dedicated to the mitigation hierarchy only included the usual suspects as a target audience, and their engagement occurred during the co-design or co-implementation phases, in some instances as consultants.

Fontaine et al. (2014) highlighted that significant values agreed on by stakeholders' active involvement are a way to improve the appreciation of the ecosystem services concept by citizens to decision-makers and to identify the owners and beneficiaries of ecological functions. The objective

to achieve consensus building implies that there are possibilities to influence, negotiate and deliberate on decisions by all stakeholders. Conflicts are a part of this kind of process, as well as the resources required for this implementation. The engagement of stakeholders not usually reached in engagement processes depends on explicit inclusion into the political agenda and the definition of clear strategies. The mapping of local participatory culture can support the identification of the stakeholder groups, their level of influence, the activities that already exist and, more importantly, how to engage them. Attention to inclusiveness ensures that under-represented priority groups, such as women, elderly people, children, immigrants, and traditional communities, are recognised. Institutionalizing citizens' engagement is a solution to the difficulties of upscaling and replicability by strengthening local and more sustainable dynamics.

Several opportunities arise from the prioritisation of this type of collaboration, also recognised as co-production, e.g., to inform the decision-making process better (Farella et al., 2016; Fontaine et al., 2014) to include a diversity of knowledge, to better evaluate the process, to include socio-cultural values and needs from a heterogeneous group of stakeholders (Barbe 2021, Sahraoui et al., 2021). The core leverage and enabling factors for the success of citizens' engagement are the transparency of the co-governance structure, the trust in the relational dynamic, the communication and interaction among all participants, the inclusion of different groups, the quality of deliberation and the co-production opportunities (see Box 2 for a possible method). Despite the numerous benefits, possible challenges, such as delays and problems in getting the stakeholders to respond, need to be considered as potential problems.

Box 2. Strategy games – one way for a meaningful stakeholder engagement

One way to explore trade-offs and consequences of different land-use scenarios are strategy games (Garcia et al 2022). Strategy games provide an opportunity to test probable impacts of different land-use scenarios and policies and find solutions that are acceptable to different stakeholders. The way the games are designed makes it possible for stakeholders to experience the consequences of decisions from the perspective of other stakeholders and engage in collaborative learning. Through the collective, explicit, and transparent problem exploration and solution identification processes, power imbalances can be revealed and addressed, and mental models updated to better correspond with realities of different stakeholders. This form of decision-making counterbalances hidden, unformulated and/or opaque decision-making processes and should lead to improved outcomes in land-use decisions because stakeholders jointly agree on the future they want to see.

Source: Garcia, C. A., Savilaakso, S., Verburg, R. W., Stoudmann, N., Fernbach, P., Sloman, S. A., Peterson, G. D., Araújo, M. B., Bastin, J.-F., Blaser, J., Boutinot, L., Crowther, T. W., Dessard, H., Dray, A., Francisco, S., Ghazoul, J., Feintrenie, L., Hainzelin, E., Kleinschroth, F., ... Waerber, P. O. (2022). Strategy games to improve environmental policymaking. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(6), 464–471. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00881-0>

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Experiencing consequences of management and policy decisions through playing.

5.3.3. Social drivers of avoidance: Mainstreaming ecosystem services as part of the mitigation hierarchy

The advisability of including ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy has been deeply debated by the panel and in the literature. The general conclusion is that ecosystem services should be mainstreamed into the mitigation hierarchy in an attempt to address biodiversity values from a broader perspective, raising awareness of the societal benefits of nature conservation and highlighting the dependency on nature for the livelihoods of different stakeholder groups. The integration of ecosystem services provides the opportunity to better connect biodiversity issues with social challenges in the context of specific decision-making processes, allowing the meaning and implications of concepts to be expanded, such as impact “mitigation” and “No Net Loss”, and to use different types of valuation approaches, methods and indicators (see Box 3). In addition, the separation of ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation would not be consistent with the idea that biodiversity is essential to support all ecosystem services and that conservation and sustainable use of ecosystems and their services are part of the same issue. However, concerns emerged related to the risk that the inclusion of ecosystem services could be disadvantageous to biodiversity (e.g., in cases where the conservation or enhancement of specific ecosystem services will be considered an acceptable substitute for biodiversity loss). Concerns related particularly to the fact that biodiversity might be downplayed against more vocal and organised interest groups that might favour, for example, provisioning services or, more generally, services that can be easily measured and quantified.

5.4. Effective avoidance: What to avoid and how

It is clear from the results (see the section on “Avoidance as a concept”) that there is a need for a proactive approach to ensure effective avoidance. One approach that came up in the research process is landscape-scale mapping of biodiversity and sensitive ecosystems along with their relevant ecosystem services. It was emphasised that there is a need to bring scientists and stakeholders together in a mutual learning process, linking expert and local knowledge(s). The aim of this process would be to implement meaningful territorial strategies and build local capacity to understand and implement the strategies in an inclusive process. Estonia is an example where landscape scale mapping of ecosystem services has begun (see Box 4)

As one of the panellists pointed out, mapping cultural ecosystem services can be difficult. Still, the expert working group is aware of methodologies that could be helpful here, for example, Bachi et al. (2020), Crossman et al. (2013) and Ribeiro and Ribeiro (2016). A multi-species approach is also important at the landscape scale that takes into account the varying vulnerabilities of each species. For example, there is a need to consider the mobility of species through the landscape and their varying sensitivity to habitat fragmentation. Trade-offs are inevitable in such approaches, but it is our opinion from the sum of the evidence that it is easier to minimise these trade-offs at the landscape scale rather than purely protected area level to ensure the maximum ecological benefit for a greater number of species. Thus, ensuring functional connectivity of vulnerable areas supports movement across landscapes and promotes avoidance of impacts at the species level. As the literature states, however, these trade-offs do need to be identified and managed in a transparent manner. This is particularly important in cases where species have large spatial requirements. Thus,

Box 3. Integration of ecosystem services to design more equitable mitigation strategies.

Mandle et al. (2015) developed an approach to mitigate the negative impacts from development that tracks how people are affected by environmental degradation. The approach combines an ecosystem services modeling framework with data on where people live and how they rely on benefits from ecosystems, and use the information to design more equitable mitigation strategies than would be created by simply focusing on biodiversity or ecosystem services. The approach is illustrated for a case study in road development, focusing on four ecosystem services (sediment retention, nitrogen regulation, phosphorus regulation and carbon storage), which are likely to be unaccounted for in classic impact assessment. They have a clear importance to local stakeholders and are likely to be affected by the proposed road. The concept of “servicshed” (i.e., the area that provides a particular ecosystem service to a particular beneficiary, Tallis et al. 2016) is applied to determine the location and degree of mitigation needed to offset the impact on ecosystem services to those people who would be negatively affected by the road construction. This approach allows to transparently assess the equity of the positive and negative environmental impacts resulting from development and mitigation actions. It also makes apparent how these impacts are distributed across the landscape and different segments of the society.

Source: Mandle et al. 2015. Who loses? Tracking ecosystem services redistribution from road development and mitigation in the Peruvian Amazon.

Tallis, H., Kennedy, C.M., Ruckelshaus, M., Goldstein, J., Kiesecker, J.M. 2016. Mitigation for the people: an ecosystem services framework. In: Geneletti, D (Ed). Handbook on biodiversity and ecosystem services in impact assessment. Edward Elgar Publishing, 41-61.

landscape mapping of the functional ecological units can highlight where further fragmentation of the landscape can be avoided and draw attention to the potential threats from multiple sources as well as their cumulative impacts.

Buffer zones can also be identified around sensitive habitats in need of protection, and habitats can be connected to ensure the long-term sustainability of biodiversity. Development of this blue and green infrastructure has the potential to support not just biodiversity but also a range of ecosystem services, such as food provisioning; improving water quality from agricultural agrochemicals and urban runoff; and biomass production for novel products and energy as part of the bioeconomy initiatives within the EU. It is therefore important not just to map biodiversity but also ecosystem services that people rely on to ensure a holistic overview of dynamic landscapes and the underlying processes to be able to minimise the trade-offs incurred.

Furthermore, landscape connectivity frameworks based on single or multi-species, including habitat networks, are popular approaches within the mitigation hierarchy (Berges et al., 2020; Préau et al., 2022). A connectivity approach based on species observations provides good insights not only to tackle avoidance, reduction but also to develop scenarios of compensation oriented towards planning (see Box 5 for an example). A habitat connectivity framework for the mitigation hierarchy provides direct benefits providing practical recommendations to be implemented at the local to the regional level (e.g., Préau et al., 2022a; Préau et al., 2022b). In addition, a well-conducted connectivity analysis for target species shows the multifunctionality and gain for certain species when mitigation measures are in place. Providing measures and scenarios based on connectivity approaches would improve the overall ecological network (Clauzel and Godet 2020) and thus provide a set of ecosystem services (Keesstra

et al., 2018, Liquette et al., 2016), as well as increasing the potential for species to adapt to climate change (Chausson et al., 2020).

An Applied Delphi panellist stated that in practice, the alternatives to avoidance are never costly enough and therefore, offsets are regularly used to compensate for biodiversity loss. Despite the fact that if ecological compensation is done properly and all uncertainties are taken into account, it is costly, we would argue from the evidence that the avoidance stage is still essential for many vulnerable areas, both in protected areas and unprotected areas, where those habitats are simply irreplaceable. No amount of offsetting will compensate for their loss. Ecosystem services may be of benefit but difficult to account for in the case of non-monetary benefits. Thus, avoidance should be the priority. A landscape-scale analysis should identify these irreplaceable areas and the necessary green infrastructure to support their integrity and the species that depend on them before any offsets should be considered.

photo © Joanna Storie

Biodiverse semi-natural grasslands can act as green infrastructure buffer zones for protected areas.

Box 4. Estonian example of ecosystem services mapping.

Estonia has been actively mapping ecosystem services with the view of integrating the values into the planning processes of the country. The ELME project is a nationwide project to map terrestrial ecosystems and their services and LIFE IP CleanEst deals with the freshwater ecosystems. The results from both projects are meant to be used in practice.

Mapping of the biophysical ecosystem services and the condition of the ecosystems are finished and mapping of the monetary values of ecosystem services is currently ongoing. The mapping has involved some very emotional discussions, such as in the siting of wind farms with obvious divergent views of stakeholders. However, the mapping is viewed as an important step in protecting nature as it is possible to see where the most valuable ecosystems in good condition are located and makes it easier to implement nature protection in practice. It also helps planners to be aware of the ecosystem services provided by nature to stakeholders.

Estonian website for the public: <https://loodusveeb.ee/en>

photo © Joanna Storie

Vooremaa Nature Park, Estonia.

5.4.1. Effective avoidance from infrastructure projects

The effective avoidance of impacts from infrastructure projects may be addressed in certain circumstances by addressing spatiotemporal dimensions of the impacts that affect the biodiversity or local communities. It was documented by a panellist in the Applied Policy Delphi process that conservation should be considered as an ecosystem service per-se. Conservation may consist of a mix of regulations and spatiotemporal measures that can be applied to multiple ecosystem goods and services, and sectors. While the application of cumulative effects assessments is seeing increased momentum in Marine Spatial Planning (PW4B, 2023; Menegon et al., 2018), their application in territorial planning still needs further work. Overall, the cumulative effects exerted by a development project need to be determined by identifying the physical (e.g., soil sealing), ecological (e.g., chemical pollutants, nutrients), and energy-related (e.g., electromagnetic field, light or noise pollution) pressures. In addition, there is a need to examine how the impacts affect biodiversity and societal dimensions regarding the sectors that depend on the impacted ecosystem. An operational framework for identifying pressures is provided for aquatic environments: Annexe III of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), which identifies the pressures exerted by anthropogenic coastal and marine activities. The advantage of the pressure framework is that it is 1) possible to formalise avoidance measures in spatiotemporal terms (pressure and intensity-based avoidance buffers, wildlife-specific avoidance buffers, and seasonal avoidance buffers); 2) pressure propagation patterns (e.g., buffers of influence) can be defined and 3) the sensitivity of biodiversity components to the pressures addressed.

Other examples of the categorisation of threats and pressures are provided by Art.17 of the Habitat Directive and Art. 12 of the Birds Directive (EIONET, 2015). This is used to report species and conservation status and address particular threats and pressures in protected sites.

Technological innovations and design can, in some cases, further alleviate the impacts of infrastructure projects on biodiversity. However, they may bring with them uncertainty with new and diversified pressures and pressure mechanisms on biodiversity. The cancellation of infrastructure projects should be considered if technology and design lead to high uncertainty of impacts on biodiversity and society. To increase the effectiveness of avoidance mechanisms of the infrastructure project, it should be identified how the social dimension could be included in the avoidance measures.

5.5. Improving implementation through stakeholder engagement and Capacity building

The scientific evidence underlines the complexity and dynamic nature of the issues involved and the necessity to clarify definitions and terminology to ensure common understanding. However, it is also important to construct narrative accounts that are specific to a place, as each landscape unit presents unique challenges to biodiversity and the people who live and work in that landscape. Building the capacity to understand this natural capital across sectors is critical.

There are several challenges regarding stakeholder engagement and capacity building. These include, for example, the limited knowledge of the participants, the loss of motivation of the public authorities and organisations, and insufficient

Box 5. French example avoidance for territorial planning

For connectivity assessments, context prioritisation is likely to differ depending on the species considered. These decisions are key for territorial planning. Here, we provide an example of areas identified in six urban sprawl projects inside a local management scheme (SCOT) in the South of France in the territory of the Thau Lagoon, to demonstrate the methodological approach. The objective was to assess the relevance of identifying priority areas for connectivity of groups of species based on common dispersal abilities. We aimed to address avoidance by assessing the impact of target groups' choices on predicted priority areas. The choice of species was made in agreement with stakeholders in accordance with their interest in biodiversity conservation measures and the knowledge base to be implemented. Ecological niche modelling was used to quantify species resistance and to identify suitable habitat patches and connectivity (see Preau et al. 2022). We found important differences in identified priority areas between groups with dissimilar dispersal abilities, with little overlap between highly connected areas. We identified a gap between the level of protection of low dispersal species and highly connected areas. We found mismatches between existing corridors and connectivity in low dispersal species and a greater impact in areas of expected urban sprawl projects on favourably connected areas for species with high dispersal capabilities.

This study demonstrates the importance of selecting a diversity of species with different dispersal capacity ranges to identify ecological corridors in programmes that aim to restore habitat connectivity at territorial levels. These findings are oriented to support decisions of planning initiatives at both local and regional scales working in tandem with local knowledge and stakeholders.

For more details: Preau C, Dubos N, Lenormand M, Denelle P, Le Louarn M, Alleaume S & Luque S (2022) Dispersal-based species pools as sources of connectivity area mismatches. *Landscape Ecology* 37, 729-743. [arXiv][pdf][code] [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01371-y\(0123456789\)](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01371-y(0123456789)).

funding for implementation. These all pose a risk for conflicts, lead to response delays and affect institutional capacity.

According to the results from the Applied Policy Delphi process, greater transparency generates numerous positive effects on decision-making processes. The transparency is underlined as crucial for education and capacity, both associated with the validation, enforcement and monitoring process. Moreover, the degrees of power to influence decisions were pointed out through two approaches suggested for further exploration, the power imbalances associated with equity distribution and power dynamics related to the efficacy of the decision-making process.

It is recommended from the results that active participation should be encouraged by raising awareness through better, solid background information about the ecological status of the ecosystems (or the site-specific ecosystem). In this sense, specific language, tailored formats and appropriate communication channels to engage the different stakeholder groups and to ensure the “translation” of technical information into language easily understood is also recommended. These strategies can improve the transparency process, at the same time that it educates individuals and institutions to enhance the mitigation hierarchy impacts (see box 6 for an example).

photo © Joama Storie

Education and capacity building are needed to understand the site-specific ecosystems and the role that biodiversity plays. Which are the pests, and which are the beneficial species? Who benefits, and who loses?

Box 6. Multi-stakeholder collaboration to create an operational model for municipalities to implement mitigation hierarchy

A multi-stakeholder process was used in the No Net Loss City project in Finland to develop an operational model for municipalities to effectively use mitigation hierarchy in their land-use planning, and where needed, implement biodiversity offsets (Hohti et al. 2022). The development process was built on collaboration between researchers and practitioners and combined researchers' scientific knowledge on ecological compensation with practitioners' knowledge about land-use planning processes.

At the beginning, objectives for the work were jointly defined. Based on these objectives, the development for practical solutions took place in four workshops, which had different themes. The first workshop focused on knowledge needs and challenges of biodiversity offsets, in the second workshop a preliminary operational model was introduced and discussed, and compensation was looked at more in detail (e.g. ecological values to be compensated, data availability). The third workshop focused on land-use planning and decision making in municipalities, the processes, and responsibilities. In the fourth workshop the operational model was finalised. Overall, 40 people participated in the process. Of those, 13 were experts on land-use planning at municipality level, 18 were researchers, and 9 people represented other stakeholders. Two of the workshops were held virtually and two in person. The whole process took around 9 months to complete. The operational model is being piloted in Jyväskylä, a mid-sized city in Finland.

More information can be found here: <https://boostbiodiversityoffsets.fi/en/>.

Source: Hohti, J., Nieminen, E., Jalkanen, J., Oinonen, I., Huttunen, S., Pappila, M., Halme, P., Salokannel, V., Pietilä, K., Kujala, H. (2022). Kunnat hidastamaan luontokatoa – Suosituksia luontohaittojen välttämiseksi, lieventämiseksi ja kompensoimiseksi kuntien maankäytössä. Wisdom Letters.

Conclusions

6. Conclusions

The aim of this report was to provide evidence-based knowledge on if and how ecosystem services can be considered in projects, programmes, policies and associated impact assessments with a particular focus on the avoid stage of the mitigation hierarchy. The focus was:

1. To gather knowledge on how ecosystem services/natural capital as concepts foster the conservation and enhancement of biodiversity within planning processes in sectors that are likely to have a direct impact on biodiversity.
2. To identify EU-wide cases and practices that actively consider and address the aspect of ecosystem services in the mitigation hierarchy.
3. To develop guidance on best practices and information on:
 - › a. If and how the consideration and operationalisation of ecosystem services can be integrated into natural capital assessments, impact assessments, and policymaking processes to enhance biodiversity conservation;
 - › b. What kind of impacts and challenges may occur when the ecosystem services concept is used in the mitigation hierarchy and similar processes; and
 - › c. How replicable and transferable are tools and processes in countries or regions that have been used successfully in the avoid stage?

We conclude that ecosystem services can be mainstreamed into the mitigation hierarchy. However, care will need to be taken to ensure that biodiversity and life-serving ecosystem services are prioritised and safeguarded over those ecosystem services that grant economic profits. Integrating ecosystem services into mitigation hierarchy and land-use planning processes is also an opportunity for improved stakeholder engagement. By engaging with local stakeholders in an area from the very early stages, land-use planners and decision-makers can integrate stakeholder values and perspectives into planning and ensure land-use planning is driven by local experience and knowledge, together with the best available scientific evidence.

We did not find much evidence of the use of the ecosystem services concept in the mitigation hierarchy. Therefore, we cannot give an evidence-based answer to the question of what impacts may occur when the ecosystem concept is used in the

mitigation hierarchy. When we look at the identified impacts on biodiversity, it is clear that impacts occur across different spatial and temporal scales and can be synergistic, antagonistic or dominant.

In practice, a lack of resources is the biggest challenge to ensuring effective design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation practices. Other identified challenges were a lack of clear definitions, effective regulation, capacity building and true stakeholder engagement and collaboration.

None of the challenges identified are insurmountable nor novel in environmental governance and land-use planning. Nor are we lacking solutions to address them. In this report, we provide examples of solutions and tools and practices that are transferable and replicable from one context to another. Within the upscaling process, we recommend that the information produced is made accessible to a broad set of stakeholders and to adapt communication strategies to different target audiences to ensure a wide reach of knowledge.

Finally, we conclude that putting biodiversity first and avoiding further loss is both possible and needed for the benefit of society and the planet we live on. Moving towards sustainability requires fundamental transformations, including changes in how biodiversity is perceived and valued. Newly established relations between societal actors are also required. This demands a holistic vision for the maintenance of biodiversity that balances conservation and mitigation processes and the sustainable provision of ecosystem services. The mitigation hierarchy and its effective implementation are central to fulfilling this vision. The recommendations in this report provide a roadmap on how to do this. However, they are only effective if decision-makers, land use planners and practitioners commit to improving legislation and practices. Hence, we end our report with a call for action to all those involved in land-use planning: it is time to act to get effective mitigation practices put into place before tipping points are reached.

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French law on national engagement for the environment (n° 2010-788 of 12 July 2010) Web: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/dossierlegislatif/JORFDOLE000020078758/> last access 27/02/2023.

Legal sources without binding effects

Proposal for a Regulation of the EU Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration, 22.6.2022, COM(2022) 304 final.

J. Maes and others, Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: An EU ecosystem assessment, EUR 30161 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-17833-0, doi:10.2760/757183, JRC120383.

Commission Notice Guidance document on wind energy developments and EU nature legislation, Publications Office, 18.11.2020, C (2020) 7730 final.

Commission Notice Managing Natura 2000 sites – The provisions of Article 6 of the ‘Habitats’ Directive 92/43/EEC, 21.11.2018, C(2018) 7621 final.

Commission Staff Working Document ‘Action Plan on the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 A disaster risk-informed approach for all EU policies’, 16.6.2016 SWD (2016) 205 final.

Commission’s Guidance on Implementation of Directive 2001/42 on the Assessment of the Effects of Certain Plans and Programmes on the Environment, 12.03.2004.

European Parliament Resolution of 21 September 2010 on the Implementation of EU Legislation Aiming at the Conservation of Biodiversity (2009/2108(INI)), OJEU (2012/C 50 E/03).

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, ‘The European Green Deal’, COM/2019/640 final.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, ‘EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing Nature Back into our Lives’, COM/2020/380 final.

Commission Notice ‘Guidance document on Wind Energy Developments and EU Nature Legislation’, 18.11.2020 C (2020) 7730 final.

The EIB (European Investment Bank) Group Climate Bank Roadmap 2021-2025 of 14 December 2020, DOI:10.2867/503343.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing nature back into our lives, 20.5.2020, COM/2020/380 final.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions ‘EU Soil Strategy for 2030 Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate’, COM/2021/699 final.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, COM/2021/82 final.

Annexes

Annexe 1: The performance of the search string. (The final search string is in bold)

SEARCH STRING	HITS (WOSCC)	HITS (SCOPUS)	DATE	WHO DID THE SEARCH	WHICH ACCESS	COMMENTS	TEST LIST ARTICLES FOUND IN WOSCC	ARTICLES NOT FOUND IN TESTING
"Mitigation hierarchy" AND "avoid\$stage"	0		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
"Mitigation hierarchy"	125		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
"mitigation hierarchy" AND avoid*	58		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigation AND avoid AND biodiversity	317		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigat* AND avoid* AND biodiversity	516		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigat* AND (avoid* OR prevent*) AND biodiversity	966		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigat* AND (avoid* OR prevent*) AND biodiversity AND Europ*	219		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigat* AND (avoid* OR prevent*) AND "ecosystem service**"	452		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigat* AND (avoid* OR prevent*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity)	1230		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(biodiversity OR "ecosystem services") AND mitigat*	9328		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity)	11530		19.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
"mitigation hierarchy" AND biodiversity	111		21.7. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
mitigation AND hierarchy	894	988	25.8. 2021	Sylvie Campagne	CNRS, France			
mitigation AND hierarchy AND avoid	71	56	25.8. 2021	Sylvie Campagne	CNRS, France			
mitigation AND hierarchy AND "ecosystem services**"	48	35	25.8. 2021	Sylvie Campagne	CNRS, France			

SEARCH STRING	HITS (WOSCC)	HITS (SCOPUS)	DATE	WHO DID THE SEARCH	WHICH ACCESS	COMMENTS	TEST LIST ARTICLES FOUND IN WOSCC	ARTICLES NOT FOUND IN TESTING
mitigation AND hierarchy AND ("ecosystem services*" OR biodiversity)	143	160	25.8. 2021	Sylvie Campagne	CNRS, France			
mitigation hierarchy "ecosystem services*" biodiversity			25.8. 2021	Sylvie Campagne	CNRS, France			
avoid* AND "ecosystem services**	1156							
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR aesthet* OR "air quality" OR aquacultur* OR art OR assimilat* OR attenuat* OR biodiversity OR biofilt* OR "biogeochemical services" OR biomass OR bioremediation OR biosecurity OR birdwatching OR buffer* OR catch OR "coastal protection" OR cognitive OR conservat* OR control OR cultur* OR denitrificat* OR deposit* OR detoxific* OR disease OR diversity OR "ecosystem services" OR ecosystem* OR ecotouris* OR filter* OR fish* OR habitat OR harvest* OR hunting OR identity OR improve* OR informat* OR inspirat* OR leisure OR minerali* OR mitigat* OR "non-consumptive use" OR nursery OR "nutrient cycl*" OR "nutrient recycl*" OR pest OR photosynthesis OR pollinat* OR prevention OR product* OR provision* OR purificat* OR "quality maint**" OR "raw materials" OR recreat* OR reduct* OR refug* OR regenerat* OR regulat* OR remov* OR research OR resources OR retent* OR sequestrat* OR stabilisation OR storage OR touris* OR treatment OR uptake OR "water quality" OR wildlife)	2248362		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR aesthet* OR "air quality" OR aquacultur* OR biofilt* OR "biogeochemical services" OR bioremediation OR biosecurity OR birdwatching OR "coastal protection" OR denitrificat* OR deposit* OR detoxific* OR ecotouris* OR filter* OR hunting OR leisure OR minerali* OR "non-consumptive use" OR "nutrient cycl*" OR "nutrient recycl**" OR pest OR photosynthesis OR pollinat* OR prevention OR product* OR provision* OR purificat* OR "quality maint**" OR recreat* OR refug* OR regulat* OR resources OR retent* OR sequestrat* OR stabilisation OR storage OR touris* OR "water quality" OR wildlife)	1298326		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	17923		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat*) AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR aesthet*)	23003		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	18758		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "nature's contribution to people") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	19773		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			

SEARCH STRING	HITS (WOSCC)	HITS (SCOPUS)	DATE	WHO DID THE SEARCH	WHICH ACCESS	COMMENTS	TEST LIST ARTICLES FOUND IN WOSCC	ARTICLES NOT FOUND IN TESTING
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	19787		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity)	19786		8.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green space" OR "blue space")	20907		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green space" OR "urban green*")			9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity) OR ("ecosystem service" OR biodiversity) NEAR5 ("land use planning" OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green space" OR "blue space")	18982		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity) OR ("ecosystem service" OR biodiversity) NEAR5 ("land use planning" OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green space" OR "urban green*"))	18982		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "impact assessment") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity) OR ("ecosystem service" OR biodiversity) NEAR5 ("land use planning" OR "blue infrastructure" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green space" OR "blue space"))	18968		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	13782		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Title, abstract and author keywords only		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	13794		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki			
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	14371		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Title, abstract and author keywords only		

SEARCH STRING	HITS (WOSCC)	HITS (SCOPUS)	DATE	WHO DID THE SEARCH	WHICH ACCESS	COMMENTS	TEST LIST ARTICLES FOUND IN WOSCC	ARTICLES NOT FOUND IN TESTING
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	20832		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "environmental services" OR "ecological services" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	21140		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	21176		9.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	21217	14964	14.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search	3/4	Almeida et al. 2018
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	21252	14985	15.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	4/4, 5/5	
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value")	21326		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "natural capital")	21404		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	6/7	Almeida et al. 2018
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people")	21301		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	6/7	Almeida et al. 2018

(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	21420		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	6/7	Almeida et al. 2018
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "marine spatial planning") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	21420		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	21467		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	21473		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND (ecosystem service* OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	21498		21.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	6/7	Almeida et al. 2018
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND (ecosystem service* OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	20512		23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	6/7	Almeida et al. 2018
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "management plan*" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal* plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	22114	26,584	23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso (WoSCC) / Sylvie Cam-pagne (Scopus)	University of Helsinki / CNRS, France	Topic search in WoSCC	7/8	Almeida et al. 2018

SEARCH STRING	HITS (WOSCC)	HITS (SCOPUS)	DATE	WHO DID THE SEARCH	WHICH ACCESS	COMMENTS	TEST LIST ARTICLES FOUND IN WOSCC	ARTICLES NOT FOUND IN TESTING
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	20512	24,817	23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso (WoSCC) / Sylvie Campagne (Scopus)	University of Helsinki / CNRS, France	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "impact assessment" OR "environmental compensation") AND ("land use planning" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "green corridors") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	406		23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC		
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "management plan*" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	22123	25959	23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC; title, abstract, keywords in Scopus	8/8	
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "management plan*" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	22117		23.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC	8/8	
(avoid* OR prevent* OR mitigat* OR "land use planning" OR "management plan*" OR "urban greening" OR "spatial planning" OR "marine planning" OR "impact assessment" OR "county plan*" OR "municipal plan*" OR "theme plan*" OR "environmental compensation" OR "green corridors" OR "functional urban area*") AND ("ecosystem service*" OR "ecosystem goods and services" OR "environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR biodiversity OR "nature's contribution to people" OR "nature value" OR "natural capital")	22163		29.9. 2021	Sini Savilaakso	University of Helsinki	Topic search in WoSCC; title, abstract, keywords in Scopus	8/8	

Annexe 2: List of articles used to test the comprehensiveness of the search string

1. Almeida, E. de L.; Nascimento, A.P.B. do; Gallardo, A.L.C.F.; Claudio, C.F.B.R. & Ruiz, M.S. (2018) Contribuições da avaliação de impacto ambiental à redução dos impactos sobre a biodiversidade em região de alto fluxo turístico em São Paulo, Brasil. *Revista Rosa dos Ventos Turismo e Hospitalidade*, 10(3), pp. 464-482. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18226/21789061.v10i3p464>.
2. [Contributions of Environmental Impact Assessment to Reduce Impacts on Biodiversity in a High Tourism Flow Region in São Paulo, Brazil]
3. Laurent Bergès, Catherine Avon, Lucie Bezombes, Céline Clauzel, Rémi Dufлот, Jean-Christophe Foltête, Stéphanie Gaucherand, Xavier Girardet, Thomas Spiegelberger (2020) Environmental mitigation hierarchy and biodiversity offsets revisited through habitat connectivity modelling, *Journal of Environmental Management*. Volume 256, 109950. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109950>.
4. Hansen, K., Malmaeus, M., Hasselström, L., Lindblom, E., Norén, K., Olshammar, M., Söderqvist, T., & Soutukorva, Å. (2018). Integrating ecosystem services in Swedish environmental assessments: an empirical analysis. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 36(3), 253–264. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1445178>
5. Timo P. Karjalainen, Mika Marttunen, Simo Sarkki, Anne-Mari Rytönen (2013) Integrating ecosystem services into environmental impact assessment: An analytic–deliberative approach. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, Volume 40, Pages 54-64. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2012.12.001>.
6. Phalan, B., Hayes, G., Brooks, S., Marsh, D., Howard, P., Costelloe, B., . . . Whitaker, S. (2018). Avoiding impacts on biodiversity through strengthening the first stage of the mitigation hierarchy. *Oryx*, 52(2), 316-324. doi:10.1017/S0030605316001034
7. Rozas-Vásquez, D., Fürst, C., & Geneletti, D. (2019). Integrating ecosystem services in spatial planning and strategic environmental assessment: The role of the cascade model. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 78(February), 106291. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2019.106291>
8. Heather Tallis, Christina M. Kennedy, Mary Ruckelshaus, Joshua Goldstein, Joseph M. Kiesecker (2015) Mitigation for one & all: An integrated framework for mitigation of development impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, Volume 55, Pages 21-34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2015.06.005>.
9. Léa Tardieu, Sébastien Roussel, John D. Thompson, Dorothée Labarraque, Jean-Michel Salles (2015). Combining direct and indirect impacts to assess ecosystem service loss due to infrastructure construction, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 152, Pages 145-157.

Annexe 3: Search strings

ORGANISATION	WEBSITE	DATE	SEARCH LANGUAGE	SEARCH STRINGS	SEARCH DE- TAILS	NUM- BER OF HITS	NUM- BER OF DUPLI- CATES	INCLUDED AT STAGE AFTER DUPLICATE REMOVAL	INCLUDED AT THE FULL TEXT STAGE	UNRE- TRIEVABLE	SCREENER	COMMENTS
ACCORAMS (The Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area)	https://accobams.org/news-publications/outreach-materials/	3/25/2022	English	Mitigation hierarchy	marine, modified to mitigation measures	12	1	1	1		Daniel	
Offshore Coalition for Energy and Nature	https://offshore-coalition.eu/publications	3/25/2022	English	Mitigation hierarchy	marine	4	1	1			Daniel	
ICES (International Council of the Exploration of the Sea)/OSPAR	https://ices-library.figshare.com/search	3/25/2022	English	Mitigation hierarchy	marine	33	0	0	1		Daniel	
HELCOM	https://helcom.fi/helcom-at-work/publications/	3/25/2022	English	Mitigation hierarchy	marine, modified to mitigation measures	1	1	1	1		Daniel	HELCOM Action Plan 2021
IUCN	https://portals.iucn.org/library/dir/publications-list		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		0					Sylvie	
IUCN	https://portals.iucn.org/library/search		EN	Mitigation hierarchy		6	4	2	2		Francesca	
OFB	https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/documentation		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		5	0	0			Sylvie	
FRB	https://www.fondationbiodiversite.fr/publications/		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		2	0	0			Sylvie	
CEREMA	https://www.cerema.fr/fr/centre-res-sources/boutique/general		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		2	0	1	1	0	Sylvie	
these.fr	https://theses.fr/		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		74	0	1	1	0	Sylvie	
IFREMER	https://archimer.ifremer.fr/search		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		16	0	1	1	0	Sylvie	
Biodiversité outre-mer	https://biodiversite-outre-mer.fr/		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		0	0	0			Sylvie	
PNDP	https://www.pndp.fr/		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		0	0	0			Sylvie	
INPN	https://inpn.mnhn.fr/accueil/index		French	ERC Eviter Compens- er Réduire		15	0	0			Sylvie	
Latvian Institute for Environmental solutions		3/3/2022	English	Mitigation hierarchy		0					Joanna	Only biodiversity turned up any links, so probably not useful
SYKE - Finnish Environment Institute	https://www.syke.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
Tiede ja tutkimus - a website that collects and shares information on research conducted in Finland	https://tiedejatutkimus.fi/fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	

Tiede ja tutkimus - a website that collects and shares information on research conducted in Finland	https://tiedejatutkimus.fi/fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Ei nettonävisiä	Shortened search string	1					Sini	The publication found was a duplicate of a publication already included into the full text stage from an other source.
Luke - Natural Resources Institute Finland	https://www.luke.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
Luke - Natural Resources Institute Finland	https://www.luke.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämis*		2	0	1	0		Sini	
Ympäristöministeriö	https://ym.fi/etusivu	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
Ympäristöministeriö	https://ym.fi/etusivu	3/23/2022	Finnish	Luontoarvojen heikentäminen		13	2	0	0		Sini	
WWF Suomi	https://wwf.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
SLL	https://www.sll.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
Birdlife	https://www.birdlife.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Lieventämishierarkia		0					Sini	
Birdlife	https://www.birdlife.fi/	3/22/2022	Finnish	Luontoarvojen heikentäminen		0					Sini	
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Skadelindringshierarkin		0						
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Förlusten av biologisk mångfald		32	1	4	0		Karoliina	
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Biodiversitet	Shortened search string	35	0	3	0		Karoliina	
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Ingen nettoförlust	Shortened search string	3					Karoliina	
Swedish Forest Society	https://www.skogssällskapet.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Skadelindringshierarkin		3	0	1	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Forest Society	https://www.skogssällskapet.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Förlusten av biologisk mångfald		3	0	1	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Forest Society	https://www.skogssällskapet.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Biodiversitet	Shortened search string	26	0	2	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Forest Society	https://www.skogssällskapet.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Ingen nettoförlust	Shortened search string	5	0	0	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Skadelindringshierarkin		0					Karoliina	
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Förlusten av biologisk mångfald		2	0	0	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Biodiversitet	Shortened search string	61	0	2	0		Karoliina	
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Ingen nettoförlust	Shortened search string	0					Karoliina	
https://www.naturvardsverket.se/	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/	3/4/2022	Swedish	Skadelindringshierarkin		2	0	1	0		Karoliina	

Annexe 4: Organisations with relevant literature on mitigation hierarchy (full list of organisations)

ORGANISATION	WEBSITE
ACCOBAMS (The Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area)	https://accobams.org/news-publications/outreach-materials/
Offshore Coalition for Energy and Nature	https://offshore-coalition.eu/publications
ICES (International Council of the Exploration of the Sea)/OSPAR	https://ices-library.figshare.com/search
HELCOM	https://helcom.fi/helcom-at-work/publications/
IUCN	https://portals.iucn.org/library/dir/publications-list
IUCN	https://portals.iucn.org/library/search
OFB	https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/documentation
FRB	https://www.fondationbiodiversite.fr/publications/
CEREMA	https://www.cerema.fr/fr/centre-ressources/boutique/general
these.fr	https://theses.fr/
IFREMER	https://archimer.ifremer.fr/search
Biodiversité outre-mer	https://biodiversite-outre-mer.fr/
PNDB	https://www.pndb.fr/
INPN	https://inpn.mnhn.fr/accueil/index
Latvian Institute for Environmental solutions	
SYKE - Finnish Environment Institute	https://www.syke.fi/
Tiede ja tutkimus - a website that collects and shares information on research conducted in Finland	https://tiedejatutkimus.fi/fi/
Tiede ja tutkimus - a website that collects and shares information on research conducted in Finland	https://tiedejatutkimus.fi/fi/
Luke - Natural Resources Institute Finland	https://www.luke.fi/
Luke - Natural Resources Institute Finland	https://www.luke.fi/
Ympäristöministeriö	https://ym.fi/etusivu
Ympäristöministeriö	https://ym.fi/etusivu
WWF Suomi	https://wwf.fi/
SLL	https://www.sll.fi/
Birdlife	https://www.birdlife.fi/
Birdlife	https://www.birdlife.fi/
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/
Forestry Research Institute of Sweden	https://www.skogforsk.se/
Swedish Forest Society	https://www.skogssallskapet.se/
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/
Swedish Research Council Formas	http://www.formas.se/
https://www.naturvardsverket.se/	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/

ORGANISATION	WEBSITE
Swedish environmental protection agency	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/
Swedish environmental protection agency	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/
Swedish environmental protection agency	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/
Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale	www.isprambiente.it
Umweltbundesamt	https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/
Bundesamt für Umwelt	https://www.bfn.de/
Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz	https://www.bmk.gv.at/
Umweltdachverband	https://www.umweltdachverband.at/
EUROBATS	
DG - Território	https://www.dgterritorio.gov.pt
Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas	https://www.icnf.pt
Environmental and Climate Action Ministry -	https://www.sgambiente.gov.pt
National System Geographical information	https://snig.dgterritorio.gov.pt
Ecodes	https://ecodes.org/quienes-somos

Annexe 5: Applied Policy Delphi Panel - Ethics

Briefing material

1. Introduction to the process

The Eklipse mechanism is an EU initiative established in 2016 to help governments, institutions, businesses, and NGOs make better-informed decisions when it comes to biodiversity in Europe (<https://www.eklipse.eu/>). It is set up to address specific requests made by policy-makers by gathering and synthesising existing evidence and knowledge.

This process is part of a request that the French Biodiversity Agency (OFB) made in 2020 to explore and map existing knowledge and identify knowledge gaps to improve adherence to the mitigation hierarchy using ecosystem services with a particular focus on the avoid stage (<https://eklipse.eu/request-mitigation/>).

To address this request, an Expert Working Group (EWG) was established in June 2021, which adopted a Method Protocol consisting of two main elements:

- › [A systematic mapping of the literature](#);
- › [A Delphi survey with about ten experts](#) (from the scientific, policy, and academic sector).

3. Research protocol

› **Informed consent:** according to the ethical guidelines within the EU's General Data Protection Regulation GDPR, during the data collection activities, the researchers applied two modalities of informed consent: verbal consent in the first part of the interview and written informed consent based on the models provided previously by Eklipse. During all interviews, participants were informed of its purpose, duration, recording authorisation and context of the research. Also, how the interview could be used and the institution responsible for data storage, treatment and analysis.

› **Anonymity:** following the European standards, data collected during the interviews will be audio-recorded, transcribed and anonymised, eliminating names and other identity markers and references that might identify the interviewee, except specific cases previously identified and with formal permission. The transcriptions will be kept separately from the codes that correspond to the real names of the respondents. Only the data protection officer and relevant team members will have access.

2. Overview of the Delphi survey

As you know, you are one of the experts selected for the Delphi survey. The survey is structured into a preliminary scoping interview to collect your initial view on the topic (about 45-60 min) and three rounds of an email survey, where we will ask you a few open and close-ended questions. After each round, you will be provided with a summary of the replies of the other experts. We expect each survey to require about 60-90 minutes to be completed, including the time needed to read the summary material. In the Method Protocol (pages 10-11), you can find more information about the expected content of the three rounds.

The outline of the preliminary interview includes: Introduction and Q&A about the process, as needed; Exploration of the perception of the panellist about the mitigation hierarchy and use of avoid stage; Exploration of the perception and expectation of the panellist about the outcomes of the process.

› **Data storage:** the semi-structured interviews will be stored for five years following the GDPR rules. The Eklipse Mechanism will be responsible for managing and storing all data collected. The participants will be able to request a withdrawal of their participation in the survey at any time. The Eklipse data protection officer will adopt the procedure needed. Data protection officer email: emb@eklipse.eu

› **Data protection:** Eklipse will keep on file the declarations on compliance and authorisations for collecting and processing personal **data-informed consent**. Detailed information on the informed consent procedures with regard to the collection, storage, and protection of personal data will also be kept on file, as well as templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets. The audio recorded files will be password-protected, and only team members will have access to them. The objective is to ensure compliance with the GDPR procedures and the rights and interests of the voluntary research participants.

› **Data use:** the data collected will be used within the EWG mitigation hierarchy, whose goal is to implement a research process to find out the extent to which the implementation of the hierarchy is correctly applied and ecosystem services are considered and well documented. The qualitative interviews will contribute to the Delphi Panel technique and the final report. Other uses of data collected will be exclusively for scientific purposes, with the adequate reference and citation of the source and primary research.

For further information on the purpose and lawful basis for processing your personal data, please check the Eklipse privacy policy publicly available on our website: <http://eklipse.eu/privacy-policy/>.

Declaration of consent under data protection law filled by the Expert panel.

1. Information

The members of the Expert Working Group³ on how to incorporate ecosystem services in mitigation hierarchy policy working under the frame of the Eklipse mechanism are conducting interviews. These interviews are in the context of the request put to Eklipse by the French Biodiversity Agency (OFB) about 'how can we improve adherence to the mitigation hierarchy using ecosystem services with particular focus on the avoid stage'. For reports and scientific publications, interviews will be conducted with experts from various organisations (civil society, politics, business, science).

The following personal data will be collected, processed and stored during the interviews:

- › First name and surname
- › Function
- › Professional e-mail address

The interviews may be recorded on the zoom platform and then transcribed. For the further scientific evaluation of the interview texts, all information that could lead to an identification of the interviewed person is removed from the text. In the reports and scientific publications, interviews are quoted only in excerpts and without personal reference. This ensures that the interviewed person cannot be identified by third parties.

All personal data is administered solely by those responsible. Contact data and recording of the interview are stored separately from the transcript. The video/sound recording is only stored until a transcript is created and then deleted.

The aforementioned personal data will not be processed for purposes other than those described and will not be passed on to third parties.
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⁴ Members of the Experts working group on how to incorporate ecosystem services in mitigation hierarchy policy:
Sini Savilaakso (University of Helsinki, Finland) (Co-chair)
Daniel Depellegrin (Oceans and Human Health Chair, Institute of Aquatic Ecology, University of Girona, Spain) Co-chair
Joanna Storie (Estonian University of Life Sciences) (Co-chair)
Danica Lacarac (The National Green Roof Association, Serbia) (Co-chair)
Sylvie Campagne (Station Biologique de Roscoff, CNRS and the Sorbonne University, Paris, France)
Beatriz Caitana Da Silva (Centre for Social Studies – CES, Portugal)
Davide Geneletti (University of Trento, Italy)
Ifigeneia Kagkalou (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)
Francesca Leucci (Bologna/Rotterdam/Hamburg Universities)
Sandra Luque (INRAE – Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement, France)

2. Consent

Yes, I consent to the processing of my personal data listed in section 1 above in the form of original sound recordings and transcripts of the interview for the stated purposes.

I am aware that these consents are voluntary and can be revoked at any time. A revocation, however, does not eliminate the legality of the processing retroactively, but only for the future. The revocation is to be addressed to Dr. Marie Vandewalle, Head of the Eklipse Management Body and Coordinator of Eklipse:

By e-mail: marie.vandewalle@ufz.de or by post:

Dr. Marie Vandewalle

Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ
Department of Conservation Biology & Social-Ecological Systems
Permoserstraße 15
04318 Leipzig, Germany

After receipt of the revocation, the relevant data will no longer be used and processed or immediately deleted.

Person interviewed (surname, first name in block letters, signature)

Place, date

